

MSc Dissertation Thesis

MSc in Sustainable Energy Systems

Planning Saudi Arabia's Energy Transition for 2060 with PyPSA

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Planning Saudi Arabia's Energy Transition for 2060 with PyPSA

Mission Statement

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Summary and initial literature review

In 2016, Saudi Arabia have announced its vision 2030, which aims to diversify its economy and reduce its dependency on oil [1]. As of 2020, still 99% of the electricity in the country is generated by fossil fuels [2]. However, as part of the vision, the National Renewable Energy Program (NREP) was initiated, which aims to raise the Kingdom's contribution of renewable energy generation, create a balance in the mix of local energy sources, and meet the Kingdom's carbon-reduction commitments [1]. Furthermore, the Ministry of Energy in Saudi Arabia is ramping up the use of automation systems and smart networks, ensuring the reliability of the electrical service, lowering costs, improving the power grid, and providing electricity to underserved areas [1]. Furthermore, in 2021, Saudi Arabia has announced that it will reach net zero by 2060 [3]. These objectives will take a lot of effort to attain, and the country is still behind track. Therefore, more interest and awareness have been growing for sustainable development.

Since the 1940s, power systems models have existed in various forms, with the initial focus being on energy security and affordability. Climate change policy in the twenty-first century has subsequently emerged as a key driving force behind numerous research and models, with an emphasis on pathways to achieving considerable reductions in greenhouse gas emissions [4]. PyPSA is a recently developed tool for simulating and optimizing modern electrical power systems over multiple periods, which includes models for traditional generators with unit commitment, variable renewable generation, storage units, linkage to other energy sectors, and mixed alternating and direct current networks [5]. Several projects around the globe were started to use PyPSA to model power systems, such as PyPSA-EUR, PyPSA-Africa, and finally PyPSA-Earth. This MSC Dissertation Project will focus on **‘developing a power system model that could incorporate Saudi Arabia’s 2060 net zero target using PyPSA’**.

Main aims and objectives

- To review the power system in Saudi Arabia.
- To develop a power system model for Saudi Arabia using PyPSA.
- To evaluate the system and compare the results.
- Provide insights for system improvements.

Interim targets

- Become familiar with PyPSA and keep up with its updates.
- Performing a literature review of Saudi Arabia's power system.
- Implement PyPSA in Saudi Arabia and develop a power system model.

Schedule and draft work plan

Mar 8 – Apr 26	Become familiar with PyPSA and keep up with its updates.
Apr 27 – May 20	Examination break
May 21 – Jun 14	Review the power system in Saudi Arabia.
Jun 15 – Jul 25	Implement PyPSA on Saudi Arabia and develop a power system model.
Jun 26 – Jul 30	Evaluate the model and recommend improvements.
Jul 31 – Aug 15	Dissertation write-up.

Required resources

- PyPSA software packages

Health and safety implications

As the outcome of this project is a software-based model, there are no health and safety implications except for the prolonged use of computers.

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Declaration

The supervisor and the student are satisfied that this project is suitable for performance and assessment in accordance with the guidelines set out in the course documentation.

Signed:

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to be 'M. Brown', written over a horizontal line.

Supervisor

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Student

Date: 25 Apr 2022

Abstract

Plans for energy transition are more critical than ever as the impacts of climate change intensify. Saudi Arabia is making significant efforts to reduce its emissions in contribution to the global efforts to tackle climate change through its projects Vision 2030 and the Saudi Green Initiative (SGI), where net zero target has been set for 2060. The work in this dissertation is the first attempt to forecast Saudi Arabia's net zero energy system in the year 2060. The PyPSA-Africa package, which is a derivative of PyPSA, was used to construct a variety of models for the energy system. The models built in this study consist of a base model for validation, a model for 2030 as a comparison to the Vision and a transitional period, and two models for 2060 net zero, one of which is fully renewable energy while the other incorporates direct air capture (DAC) technology. Based on the generation mix, storage capacity, network expansion, hourly dispatch, curtailment, and costs, the models were assessed, and recommendations for the energy system in 2060 were provided. A spatial resolution of 30 clusters with an hourly timestep were considered. Weather data were obtained for the full year of 2013. The findings indicate that the 2030 model has a high penetration of wind energy, mostly to satisfy nighttime demand, whereas solar energy represents around a quarter of the generation mix. In contrast, battery storage is more cost effective for meeting 2060's nighttime demand, allowing solar energy to be the predominant type of generation. The implementation of DAC technology can reduce the necessary total generation capacity by about a quarter, making it more economically beneficial than the fully renewable option, with an estimated average marginal price of 0.185 SAR/kWh. Hydrogen storage did not appear to be feasible for these models. However, A significant curtailment was noticed, which may be an opportunity for exporting electricity or producing hydrogen. The recommendations in this thesis can aid in developing policies for the country's net zero target.

Declaration of originality

I declare that this manuscript is my original work, except wherever stated otherwise. This dissertation has never been submitted for any degree or examination to any other University.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Anas Algarej', written in a cursive style.

Anas Algarej

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List Of Abbreviations

Adjustment Market	AM
Anaerobic Digestion	AD
Annual Load Supply Factor	ALSF
Average Annual Growth Rate	AAGR
Capital Expenditure	CAPEX
Carbon Capture and Storage	CCS
Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Sequestration	CCUS
Carbon Dioxide	CO ₂
Combined Cycle Gas Turbines	CCGT
Compressed Air Energy Storage	CAES
Concentrated Solar Thermal	CSP
Day Ahead Market	DA
Demand Side Management	DSM
Diesel Engines	DE
Diffusive Horizontal Irradiance	DHI
Direct Air Capture	DAC
Direct Normal Irradiance	DNI
Effective Load Carrying Capability	ELCC
Electricity & Co-Generation Regulatory Authority	ECRA
Energy System Modelling	ESM
Enhanced Oil Recovery	EOR
Feed-In-Tariffs	FIT
Fixed Operation and Maintenance	FOM
Fully Renewable	FR
GCC Interconnection Authority	GCCIA
General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans	GEBCO
Global Energy Geographic Information System	GEGIS
Global Horizontal Irradiance	GHI
Global Power Plant Database	GPPD
Greenhouse Gases	GHG
Gulf Cooperation Council	GCC
Human Development Index	HDI
Hybrid Renewable Energy Systems	HRES
Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change	IPCC
KAPSARC Energy Model for Saudi Arabia	KEM-SA
King Abdullah City for Atomic and Renewable Energy	KA-CARE
King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Center	KAPSARC
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia	KSA
Levelized Cost of Energy	LCOE
Linear Fresnel Reflector	LFR
Liquified Natural Gas	LNG

Machine Learning	ML
Marginal Pricing	MP
Middle East North Africa Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment	MENA CORDEX
Mixed Complementarity	MC
Million Tonnes per Annum	mtpa
Net Present Cost	NPC
Net Present Value	NPV
Non-linear Autoregressive Distributed Lag	NARDL
Open Cycle Gas Turbines	OCGT
Open Street Map	OSM
Our World In Data	OWID
Parabolic Trough Collectors	PTC
Pay-as-Bid	PAB
Photovoltaic	PV
Polysulphide Bromide	PSB
Pumped Storage Hydro	PSH
Python for Power System Analysis	PyPSA
Refuse Derived Fuel	RDF
Renewable Energy Systems	RES
Renewable Fraction	RF
Representative Concentration Pathway	RCP
Saline Water Conversion Corporation	SWCC
Saudi Green Initiative	SGI
Solar Tower	ST
Strength, Weakness, Opportunity and Threat	SWOT
Superconducting Magnetic Energy Storage	SMES
System Advisor Model	SAM
Underground Gas Storage	UGS
United Arab Emirates	UAE
United Kingdom	UK
Vanadium Redox Batteries	VRB
Variable Operation and Maintenance	VOM
Visual Studio Code	VSCode
Waste-To-Energy	WTE
Water & Electricity Regulatory Authority	WERA
Wind Power Density	WPD
World Database on Protected Areas	WDPA
Zinc Bromine Batteries	ZRB

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Background

Climate change is a concerning worldwide issue that is continuously growing and might lead to irreversible damage to the environment and humankind. Many countries around the world are developing policies to limit the effects of climate change by reducing carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions through the adoption of renewable energy sources, developing carbon capture technologies, and increasing the efficiency of energy usage. Climate change forecasts have been generated to evaluate the current situation and how it would change in the future with different policies. The IPCC published a report on its long-term scenarios for climate change [1]. Obviously, for a long-term evaluation of climate change, a set of assumptions must be made. A technique for encapsulating those assumptions into a collection of scenarios is the use of representative concentration pathways (RCPs). When modelling potential future climate evolution, the conditions of each scenario are taken into consideration. RCPs outline the greenhouse gas concentrations that, compared to pre-industrial levels will, by 2100, cause an overall radiative forcing increase of a target amount. Four scenarios for RCPs have been set at 2.6, 4.5, 6.0 and 8.5 watts per square metre (W m⁻²), based on the radiative forcing targets for 2100. **Table 1.1** shows the range of global average temperature increases in each scenario. The survival of life on the planet may be in danger if the impact of climate change reaches a dangerous level (i.e., RCP 8.5). More frequent and intense heatwaves and natural catastrophes, which cause fatalities and significant infrastructure and economic damage, are some of the repercussions that have already begun. The greenhouse gases' (GHG) emissions are the main cause of climate change. As seen in **Figure 1.1**, in four different scenarios, the average surface temperature is largely affected by the GHG emissions level. Therefore, lowering emissions should be of high priority for all countries of the world.

Table 1.1 Increase in the global average surface temperature [1].

RCP	Temperature change (°C) by 2081-2100
RCP2.6	0.3-1.7
RCP4.5	1.1-2.6
RCP6.0	1.4-3.1
RCP8.5	2.6-4.8

Figure 1.1 Pathways of temperature change in comparison with GHG emissions [1].

In attempts to fight climate change, some countries around the world have developed energy transition plans to lower emissions from the energy system. An example of these attempts is the “Net Zero Strategy: Build Back Greener” developed by the UK last year, following in its efforts to reduce emissions and previous plans [2]. The goals of this plan include fully carbon-free electricity generation by 2035, the provision of 5 GW of hydrogen production capability by 2030, and the setting up of four clusters for carbon capture, utilization, and storage, to absorb 20–30 MtCO₂ throughout the economy. Moreover, establishing a path for low-carbon heating devices to be used in all new homes and businesses by 2035 as well as increasing planting rates in England by three times, helping the UK reach its overall goal of 30,000 hectares of new plantings per year. This plan covers several sectors to achieve its aims, as shown in **Figure 1.2**.

Figure 1.2 Indicative pathway of emissions to 2037 by sector [2].

Another plan was developed for Germany's energy transition [3]. The main goals included cutting GHG emissions by 40%, 55%, 70%, and 80 to 95% by 2020, 2030, 2040, and 2050, respectively, in comparison to a baseline of 1990 emissions. This plan also aims towards increasing renewables penetration as well as improving the efficiency of energy use and dismantling nuclear energy reactors. A summary of its targets is shown in **Table 1.2**.

Table 1.2 Summary of Germany's energy transition plan, retrieved from [3].

	Sector	Basis year	2014	2020	2030	2040	2050
	GHG	1990	-27%	-40%	-55%	-20%	-80-95%
Renewables	Power generation		27.4%	35%	50%	65%	80%
	Final energy		13.5%	18%	30%	45%	60%
	Heating		12%	14%			
	Transport		5.6%				
Efficiency	Primary energy	2008	-8.7%	-20%		-50%	
	Power	2008	-4.6%	-10%		-25%	
	Primary energy in buildings	2008	-14.8%			-80%	
	Heating in buildings	2008	-12.4%	-20%			
	Final energy productivity	2008-2050	1.6%/yr	2.1%/yr			
	Final energy in transport	2005	1.7%	-10%			-40%
	Nuclear	2000	12761 MW	8514 MW	0 MW		

In addition, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) has announced its own plans for a future energy system. The first one is Saudi's Vision 2030, which mainly aims at diversifying the whole economy, enhancing government effectiveness, and offering a fulfilling and healthy life for its citizens¹. Diversifying the economy will be achieved through several policies that promote alternative income such as tourism and industry. In terms of the energy system, the vision aims at adopting renewable energy up to 50% and phasing out oil usage in energy generation, leaving the other 50% to be generated by gas. Oil will be predominantly used for exports for revenue to develop the country. There are plans to incorporate nuclear energy, but no specific numbers are mentioned, probably due to ongoing research. As for the power grid, many projects to expand the network are under construction, with future planned work, but no specifics have been published. Furthermore, several mega projects have been announced as part of the

¹<https://www.vision2030.gov.sa/v2030/v2030-projects/>

vision, some of which are NEOM including The Line, The Red Sea Project, Amaala, Aseer Development Project, and Diriyah Gate and Qiddiya. The majority of projects aim at promoting the country of Saudi Arabia as a tourist attraction. NEOM's location has been strategically chosen in the northwest region around the borders of Egypt and Jordan. Furthermore, the KSA hosts both Makkah and Madinah, two Muslim holy sites that draw over two million pilgrims from around the world each year for the Hajj. The population of Saudi Arabia is around 35 million, with a growth rate of 1.6% approximately. For the period 1980-2010, there was a spike in the population count with growth rates ranging from 6-3% as the years passed. A recent decline in the population growth rate is probably due to economic factors. However, the Kingdom plans to increase its population by attracting more immigrants to work in the country. An announcement was made by the Crown Prince for the Riyadh Vision project where its population is likely to increase from 7.5 million people to 15 million people. Moreover, population distribution in Saudi Arabia is almost centralized in specific areas, Riyadh the capital, Qassim, which is located north of Riyadh, Jeddah on the west coast and a collection of small cities on the east coast. **Figure 1.3** illustrates the population distribution across the KSA, which is essential for understanding demand distribution.

Figure 1.3 Population distribution of Saudi Arabia (blue areas show higher densities) [4].

These ongoing projects and population expansion plans have never been performed before in Saudi Arabia. Therefore, forecasts around it are concerning, especially with the low publicity of specific details. Furthermore, energy security has never been an issue in Saudi Arabia, except for a few cases of blackouts that were resolved. However, it still poses a challenge with the growing demand of the country.

Moreover, the environmental impact of the energy system in the KSA is enormous, with emissions growing rapidly due to the reliance on fossil fuels, as shown in **Figure 1.4**. Consequently, another initiative was developed to tackle these emissions. As part of its pledge to the Paris Agreement, the KSA announced The Saudi Green Initiative (SGI) in October 2021, just weeks before the COP26 conference. The announcement of Saudi Arabia's net zero target by 2060 was part of this initiative². The plan has two main goals, first is to reduce emissions through adopting energy efficiency approaches, implement carbon capture technology, expand public transport, and raise the renewable energy capacity. The second goal is to plant 10 billion trees all over the country in order to reduce emissions and lessen the harsh weather of the country. As for energy costs in the KSA, energy has always been affordable at a low price due to large reserves of fossil fuels which have led to a low fuel price. Furthermore, government subsidies to some sectors such as power generation and water desalination have contributed to lowering the tariffs. However, in recent years, these subsidies have been lifted gradually and public opinion has revealed dissatisfaction with the situation.

Figure 1.4 Total CO2 emissions for Saudi Arabia (ktCO2) [5].

The targets of Vision 2030 have led the Ministry of Energy in Saudi Arabia to develop an integrated energy strategy³. The strategy aims at ensuring energy security, diversifying the energy mix by utilizing renewable and nuclear energy, restructuring the electricity sector, increasing consumption efficiency, managing emissions, and adopting a circular carbon economy. The ministry has introduced many initiatives and projects in order to achieve these goals. The intention of the Renewable Energy Initiative is to study and permit new renewable energy projects, usually in partnership with the private sector. Currently, only nine renewable energy projects have been considered with a total capacity of 3.67 GW, as

²<https://www.saudigreeninitiative.org/>

³<https://www.moenergy.gov.sa/en/OurPrograms/Pages/default.aspx>

shown in **Table 1.3**. This capacity is relatively low compared to the country's ambitious vision. However, two of the projects, namely Dumat Al-Jandal wind farm and Shuaibah IPP PV, claim to have the lowest LCOE of USD 1.99 cent/kwh and 1.04 cent/kwh, respectively, based on their awarded bid price. If the two projects proceed without any cost increase, they will be a major driver for the renewable energy development in the country. Electricity and water sectors are managed by the Water and Electricity Regulatory Authority (WERA), which is part of the Ministry of Energy. WERA collects data and assesses the electricity from different generators, the power network and demand.

Table 1.3 Current renewable energy projects in Saudi Arabia.

Project	Capacity (MW)	Status
Sakaka IPP PV	300	Started operation June 2021
Dumat Al-Jandal Wind Farm	400	Under construction
Shuaibah IPP PV	600	Under construction
Rabigh IPP PV	300	Under construction
Jeddah IPP PV	300	Under construction
Qurayyat IPP PV	200	Under construction
Medina IPP PV	50	Under construction
Rafha IPP PV	20	Under construction
Sudair IPP PV	1500	Under construction

Saudi Arabia occupies around 80% of the Arabian Peninsula, which is situated in the Middle East towards the far southwest of Asia between latitudes 16°N and 33°N and longitudes 34° and 56°E. The KSA is a member of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), which consists of Qatar, the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Bahrain, Kuwait, Oman and Iraq. The country is large and mostly empty, with a total size of almost 2,000,000 km². With the exception of the southern region of the country, which is primarily mountainous, the landscape generally consists of 7 sand deserts. Furthermore, west of the country, long coastal regions of around 1,760 km run along the Red Sea, and in the east, long coastal sections of about 650 km run along the Arabian Gulf. Saudi Arabia consists of 13 administrative districts, each of which is controlled by a person connected to the Interior Ministry. Rub Al-Khali, meaning the "empty quarter" in English, is the biggest desert in the Kingdom, which covers an area of 640,000 km² southeast of the country and is uninhabited.

Plans and initiatives for sustainable energy systems require accurate forecasting and continuous assessment. One of the ways to achieve that is by using energy modelling and optimization tools such as Python for Power System Analysis (PyPSA). PyPSA helps in building power networks to detect their optimal power flow for several applications in different sectors.

1.2 Motivation and Thesis Objective

Due to the significant adoption of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar in the power systems and the ongoing concern about climate change, energy transition plans have recently attracted copious attention. The amount of emissions that Saudi Arabia produces is considerably high, as almost all of its electricity generation comes from fossil fuels. The country is currently in a significant ongoing development and several plans have been developed to mitigate emissions and switch to renewable generation. The main plans are Saudi's Vision 2030 and the Saudi Green Initiative. Both are aimed at reducing emissions and building a sustainable system.

The work in this thesis is the first attempt to investigate the future energy system of Saudi Arabia in 2060, its net zero target year. A model of the power system was developed using PyPSA through the PyPSA-Africa package, which will transition into PyPSA-Earth, covering energy models around the world. Accordingly, the work in this thesis could be used as a contribution to PyPSA-Earth. Multiple system scenarios are developed for different demand values that could represent the state of electricity demand in 2060. Another model for 2030 was developed to reflect the country's power system as a transition phase and compare it with the Vision 2030 goals. Furthermore, an additional scenario was developed to incorporate direct air capture (DAC) of CO₂ and test for optimization in the likelihood of the KSA considering the continued use of fossil fuels for electricity generation in 2060. A base model was also developed to represent the current electricity system for validation. Finally, recommendations for the energy system are proposed based on the power system models built as well as the findings of the literature.

1.3 Practical Work and Required Resources

The primary areas of practical work that were necessary to achieve the goals of the thesis are highlighted in the following list:

1. Preparing and setting up the Ubuntu 20.04.4 LTS terminal in Windows as well as VSCode. Both are required to work on PyPSA,
2. Cloning PyPSA-Africa package from its GitHub repository and downloading all the relevant data,
3. Downloading the required environment and dependencies for the package,
4. Changing the scenarios to fit the goals of the thesis,
5. Solving and working around the many errors that were encountered as part of the thesis's work,
6. Developing a script to incorporate DAC into the network and checking the results,
7. Successfully obtaining outputs of the resulting network and representing them in suitable graphs.

1.4 Thesis Outline

This thesis' remaining sections are organized and presented as follows: Chapter 2 contains a review of the literature. The methods used to produce this thesis are described in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 consists of the results of using the methods. A discussion of the findings and the limitations of the thesis are presented in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 includes conclusions and suggestions for further work and research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The provision of electricity is one of the crucial factors influencing how societies progress economically. Countries around the world are in a race for renewable energy and sustainable development [6]. In order to construct a sustainable energy sector, it is essential to examine and modify subsidies, establish a reliable legislative framework, create market-based solutions, and generate open policy environments [7]. Power system modelling and optimization can provide estimates for the future energy system to assist policy makers in making informed decisions. However, one of the main challenges to the reformation of the energy industry is increasing the accuracy and comprehensiveness of power system models. Furthermore, energy in Saudi Arabia is a growing field where the country plans the implementation of many changes. The study of various sectors and evaluation of the literature is essential in order to formulate recommendations for the future.

Figure 2.1 Literature search methodology used for selecting relevant papers.

Figure 2.1 displays the search strategy applied in this section to find relevant literature. The main resource for locating pertinent published articles in conferences or journals with a high impact factor was the Scopus search engine, which is the largest abstract and citation database of peer-reviewed literature in the world. The papers were chosen after the search results were examined, taking into account the study's scope and publication date. Finding papers concerning Saudi Arabia has involved using many search queries; a few examples are shown in **Figure 2.1**.

The organization of this chapter is as follows: The development of energy modelling tools, including PyPSA, and its underlining projects, are the subject of Section 2.1. Energy in Saudi Arabia and the study of various sectors are presented in Section 2.2. The chapter concludes with a summary in Section 2.3.

2.1 Energy Modelling

Creating computer models of energy systems in order to examine them is known as energy system modelling (ESM). These models frequently use scenario analysis to test various hypotheses on the relevant technological and economic variables. The models usually aid investigation of the system's energy efficiency, natural resource use, total cost, and emissions. The minimum system cost is frequently found through mathematical optimization. The scale of a model may be global, regional, national, local, or stand-alone. Moreover, the time span may be daily, hourly, or even less. Energy systems include many sectors such as buildings, transport, heating, industry, agriculture, and others. ESM models could include all sectors as a general energy system or explore parts of them in high resolution. The interactions between energy sources, carriers and sectors are rather complex, **Figure 2.2** shows a simple illustration of such relationships. ESM could be used to evaluate the current energy system and suggest ways to improve it and generate forecasts for a future system. Therefore, ESM plays a major role in creating energy transition plans as well as helping policymakers take more accurate decisions for sustainable development. [8] reviewed the importance and influence of ESM in power and supply sector. It was stated that modelling and optimization have been demonstrated to be effective and reliable problem-solving tools, particularly for policymakers who want to create policies based on a comprehensive scenario analysis and a thorough evaluation of alternative technologies. There are several ESM tools that have been developed, especially in the last decade. In this thesis, literature showing comparisons between some tools and PyPSA will be explored.

Figure 2.2 Relationship between energy sources, carriers, and sectors [9].

2.1.1 Energy Modelling Tools

Tools for modelling energy systems have been of interest to many researchers, private companies, and governments around the world. Processes, inputs, outputs and solving techniques differ for each one. [10] reviewed a number of energy modelling tools for renewable integration that were developed up until 2010. The study summarizes the features of 37 tools that were reviewed in terms of entities in charge, visibility and sales/download statistics, various types, analyses methods, and energy sectors as well as the penetration of renewable energy in each tool. Appendix A.1 depicts tools covered by the study and their types. Results of this study help in exploring the characteristics of many tools in order to evaluate those best fitted for each scenario. However, a number of these tools are licensed and require a form of payment for their use. Consequently, the development of open source and free tools has expanded. The openmod initiative is a project that promotes open-source software and open data for energy modelling⁴. The initiative lists a large quantity of open-source tools and compares their features. Tools of interest were ones that use the Python programming language. The modelling community makes extensive use of Python, which is relatively simple to learn and has a free application. It is accessible for all popular operating systems, including Windows, Mac OS X, and GNU/Linux. As part of its development, PyPSA was compared with other popular energy modelling tools [11]. General features of PyPSA in comparison with other software are shown in Appendix A.2. By providing a more thorough modelling of power systems, including the physics of power flow according to impedances in the network, PyPSA differentiates from typical ESM such as calliope, oemof, OSeMOSYS, and URBS. PyPSA can simulate a more general energy network utilizing link components, but it is not yet able to perform certain tasks similar to OSeMOSYS' multiyear dynamic investment. The capability of PyPSA is most closely matched by the proprietary PLEXOS software, although PLEXOS lacks non-linear power flow. Furthermore, PyPSA uses libraries such as pyomo in the optimization, in addition to its ability to utilize other solvers such as Gurobi, GLPK, CLP/CBC, and HIGHS, which is an open-source solver currently in development. PyPSA was selected for this dissertation due to its features of covering a power network on a national scale with a high spatiotemporal resolution. Moreover, its ability to perform both technical and economical optimizations, and its control of emissions were favoured. Finally, an opportunity to work with the PyPSA-Africa/Earth team and contribute to the project was presented, which was a major driver for this thesis.

On the other hand, an energy modelling tool was developed by King Abdullah Petroleum Studies and Research Center (KAPSARC) for Saudi Arabia's energy system. The KAPSARC Energy Model for Saudi Arabia (KEM-SA) is an economic equilibrium model which describes the electric power,

⁴https://wiki.openmod-initiative.org/wiki/Open_Models

petrochemicals, refining, water desalination, upstream oil and gas, and cement, which are some of the most energy-intensive sectors of the Saudi economy [12]. Each sector is housed within a separate sub-model and functions as an agent that chooses how much fuel to use, what to invest in, and which technology to employ in order to reduce costs or increase profits. By constructing a home electricity use model that is connected to KEM-SA initially, and later a transport model, the model is being upgraded for other demand-side economic sectors. **Figure 2.3** below shows the sectors and the movement of physical products between them. In comparison to PyPSA, KEM-SA is not an optimization model; it is a mixed complementarity (MC) model. Optimization problems are a sub-set of, and can be represented by, MC problems. Each sub-model optimizes, but the entire collection of sub-models does not optimize for the whole. Moreover, KEM uses GAMS for integrations but does not solve optimization problems; it also requires a paid license. KEM-SA belongs to KAPSARC, which created a webpage for the use of KEM. However, running the model on the webpage was not possible and it suggests that the already existing results of previous runs, which are all pending, are checked. Furthermore, KEM is still under development and might be a good candidate for ESM in the future.

Figure 2.3 Flowchart of KEM-SA sectors [12].

2.1.2 PyPSA

PyPSA is an open modelling framework with a sizable community of users [11]. Energy systems employ it for capacity growth and dispatch optimization. The capability for high-resolution modelling of the optimal power flow is a key feature of PyPSA. PyPSA is, hence, well adapted to large-scale models that incorporate traditional generators with unit commitment, intermittent wind and solar generation, storage units, connectivity to other energy sectors, and mixed alternating and direct current networks. Since PyPSA was established in 2017, many papers have been published concerning its use and development. There are three major initiatives that were built on PyPSA which are attracting attention. First is PyPSA-EUR, a high-resolution model of the European electricity system at the transmission grid

level [13]. Second is PyPSA-EUR-SEC, which is an extension of PyPSA-EUR that incorporates demand and supply for the following sectors: transportation, space and water heating, biomass, industry, and industrial feedstocks, except for waste management, agriculture, forestry, and land use, which completes the energy system and contains all sources of greenhouse gas emissions⁵. Third is PyPSA-Africa, which has the objective of creating a strong energy system model for Africa and beyond [14]. Currently being developed, the tool will strongly draw inspiration from PyPSA and PyPSA-Eur. PyPSA-Africa is also transitioning into PyPSA-Earth and PyPSA-Earth-SEC, which will allow users to model energy systems around the world using open data. Currently, PyPSA-Africa, as part of its expansion, can be applied to many countries around the world, and its models have been used in this thesis. PyPSA-Africa project uses a number of work packages, explained in detail by [14], and are laid out as follows:

- Modelling demand,
- Modelling of conventional generators,
- Modelling Renewable Energy Systems (RES),
- Modelling with Land Cover Constraints,
- Modelling of networks and substations,
- Data creation and verification.

In addition to PyPSA-Africa and PyPSA-EUR, it is also worth mentioning other projects that have used PyPSA for energy modelling of nations. [15] created a model for the Vietnamese electricity system in order to develop plans for 2030. The model used different weather datasets, ERA5 and MERRA-2, and found differences that have a significant effect on the cost-optimized power system design. Furthermore, the South Africa energy model was developed by [16] to produce investment and operation plans for wind and solar integration. The main finding of this model was that reducing CO₂ emissions will lead to a 20% cost increase. Interestingly, PyPSA has been partially used to model the energy system of Saudi Arabia by [17]. Two sites are taken into account in the case study: the first is Sharourah in the south and the second is Al Ula in the northwest. However, the objective of the study was only to answer the question: “Is it possible to predict the Effective Load Carrying Capability (ELCC) for a mixed expansion plan, where conventional technologies and renewable energy sources are considered in parallel, while the ELCC calculation is done for PV, Wind, CSP, and GT expansions independently?”. The paper found that the most cost-effective systems exhibit penetration for PV of above 80% and for wind of above 55% on peak demand for both locations were due to not limiting RES to minimize losses within the system. It was also discussed that before any curtailment is considered, it needs to meet between 30 and 40% of peak demand using renewable technology, depending on the location. The findings of this study are thought-

⁵<https://pypsa-eur-sec.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

provoking and require further deliberation. However, the study is not comparable to the aims of this thesis. Furthermore, the model developed for the study was not published as an open model.

2.2 Energy in Saudi Arabia

As climate change effects are increasing rapidly, research on energy in Saudi Arabia has been growing in recent years. However, the number of papers is still relatively low, and the quality of research is concerning, since some papers have a low citations record and are published in journals with a low cite score. Consequently, several studies of this nature have been included and discussed in reviews of this topic. Many papers have been reviewed based on the sector of energy, other related topics and the type of analysis followed. More attention has been given to recent studies.

Saudi Arabia's plans for diversifying the economy and adopting renewable energy by 2030 has been discussed in several scientific articles that cover the transition from different sectors. Nevertheless, an evaluation of the energy transition of Saudi Arabia as a whole has not commenced apart from the work of [18]. The paper followed a review of literature to study the advancement of renewable energy sources, adjustments to energy subsidies, interventions in the built environment and energy-intensive sectors. The study stated that key energy transition indicators point to some progress in reducing energy use and intensity of carbon emissions, particularly in the residential sector. Furthermore, significant energy subsidy reforms have provided the funding for the growth of renewable energy sources. Additionally, increased engagement and competition in the energy markets is becoming more common. The paper also discussed that low-carbon cities and boosting energy efficiency in buildings through the development of construction codes are other positive parts of the energy transition. Moreover, energy-intensive industries such as desalination and petrochemicals are encouraged to adopt and promote the usage of renewable energy. Overall, the Saudi energy transformation has been more thorough than previous initiatives and has been a significant factor in the encouragement of economic empowerment and low-carbon lifestyles [18]. This study is the first to discuss the progress of Saudi Arabia's plans for energy system transition towards 2030. Nevertheless, further research is recommended in that field. The following sections review the literature of several sectors and energy sources related to Saudi Arabia's energy system.

2.2.1 Fossil Fuels

Saudi Arabia has always been reliant on fossil fuels for economic development and electricity generation. However, in recent years, interest has been growing on how to diversify the economy and implement energy generation from renewable sources. Generally, fossil fuels in KSA are used for electricity generation, transport, industry, and exportation.

a. Oil

It is well-known that oil is the primary source of energy in Saudi Arabia, and the driver of its economy. Saudi Arabia has a share of 17.2% of the world's oil reserves, which ranks it the second in global oil reserves [19]. In 2018, approximately 87% of the budgetary income, 42% of GDP, and 90% of export earnings came from the oil sector [20]. Exports of oil are also essential for generating foreign currency to meet the nation's import needs. Any disruption in this industry will probably have an impact on the economy at national and individual levels [21]. Therefore, the fluctuation of oil prices raises a major threat to the Saudi economy. Historically, the global market has seen oil as a reliable commodity. However, the drop in oil prices from 2015 to 2018 severely hurt oil exporting nations, bringing many of them to the verge of recession or, at the least, economic crisis, which has prompted the Saudi government to enact new taxes, penalties, and fines that have greatly agitated the Kingdom [22]. A simulation was performed in [23] that makes use of the Markov switching regression model, and it revealed that the fluctuation of crude oil prices has a detrimental effect on Saudi Arabia's overall industrial return. The volatility of oil prices raises a threat to the Kingdom's economy. [24] have attempted to quantify the risk premium and found that it lies between 1.3% and 4.8% depending on the planning horizon. Consequently, with increased fluctuations in recent years, the oil price could rise further to accommodate the risk on social cost. Contrarily, revenue from oil has helped the country, as [25] has shown that the Saudi Arabian human development index (HDI) is significantly influenced by oil exports using time series data from 1990 to 2016, where an increase in oil production of 100 million barrels will result in a 4%-point gain in HDI.

However, it has been proven that oil production and use increases CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere. [26] hypothesized that the trading and usage of oil have a significant environmental influence on the country, one that spans both the short and long-term. These environmental repercussions largely manifest in the nation as a higher rate of CO₂ emissions and last for a longer time. If free trade occurs through the energy sector, it is believed that it will also have an impact on the nation's CO₂ emissions. Furthermore, a study using the non-linear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) technique found that the consumption of petroleum and natural gas is a key factor in the expansion of growing economies that produce oil, yet it is still a major source of CO₂ emissions [27]. The relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emissions is clearly illustrated in **Figure 2.4**, where it shows that emissions from exported products are higher than from imported ones, due to the large exports of oil and its derivatives, and how it correlates with the country's GDP.

Figure 2.4 Emissions from the consumption and production of oil, in comparison to GDP [28].

Additionally, a study published in Nature attempted to calculate the effects of non-oil income per capita, the revenue share from the oil industry, urbanization, and gas prices on the CO₂ emissions per capita in Saudi Arabia from 1970 to 2014, using the nonlinear cointegration method to calculate the asymmetrical impacts of the oil sector on CO₂ emissions [29]. Moreover, a positive asymmetrical effect of oil income share on CO₂ emissions was discovered. Other favourable effects on CO₂ emissions are seen when the oil income share is rising rather than falling. Furthermore, it was found that the impact of a rising oil income share is greater than the effects of non-oil income, urbanization, and gas price. It is recommended that in order to maintain a cleaner environment, the economy should also reduce its reliance on the oil sector. In addition, [30] found that a rise in real income drives an increase in CO₂ emissions, while the opposite is false, using time series data from 1971 to 2013.

Since Saudi Arabia is considered the largest producer and exporter of oil worldwide, most of the oil produced in the country is exported for revenue [31], whereas around a quarter of it is consumed domestically (2.9 million barrels per day) [31]. Domestic consumption of oil in electricity generation varies with time based on demand, where the highest consumption is at peak load, with an average consumption of approximately 477 thousand barrels per day, as shown in **Figure 2.5**. Hence, the amount of oil used for power generation is relatively low compared to the total production and consumption of oil. There is a lack of literature on the usage of oil and its prospects in electricity generation in KSA. However, most studies when discussing the future of energy mix in Saudi Arabia have excluded oil from being used for power generation, which is also one of the goals of the country's Vision 2030. Oil still plays a major part in the economic development of the country and will help in establishing a strong economic stand to invest in sustainable development. The majority of the discussed studies suggested diversifying the economy and being less financially reliant on oil, which is the main aim of Saudi's Vision 2030. In addition, phasing out oil from the generation mix will reduce CO₂ emissions, especially

the production-based CO₂ emissions. However, other measures have been recommended to reach a net zero goal, such as carbon capture, utilization, and sequestration (CCUS) as well as DAC. These measures could be implemented to accommodate for the consumption-based CO₂ emissions, which are higher for KSA. Furthermore, the local price, which is low in comparison with the global price of oil derivatives, could be a potential issue in the long run; government subsidies on oil products are recommended for redirection to more sustainable technologies.

Figure 2.5 Varying power generation from oil in Saudi Arabia [31].

b. Natural Gas

Natural gas is more environmentally friendly than coal and oil, and it is the preferred fuel for combined cycle power plants due to their higher thermal efficiency [32]. Gas has not been a strong asset in the economy of Saudi Arabia in relation to exports. However, the country does not import gas either. Therefore, all natural gas produced in Saudi Arabia is consumed locally in power generation, heating, petrochemical industries, and injections for oil extraction [32], as shown in **Figure 2.6**. Saudi Arabia has a share of 3.2% of the world's gas reserves, which ranks it the sixth in global gas reserves [19]. This share has been maintained since around 1988 [33]. The impact of natural gas usage to Saudi Arabia's real GDP has been studied in [34] with long-term time series data from 1968 to 2016 in a multivariate framework that incorporates total trade as a new variable, using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag method of cointegration. The study hypothesized that a strategy for natural gas conservation would reduce the demand for gas, impede global trade and, hence, reduce domestic output. However, by embracing renewable energy solutions to natural gas in the near future, the government may be able to satisfy energy needs and improve overall commerce. [35] described the different gas sources in the Kingdom and the potential of natural gas in the development of Saudi Arabia. This study has concluded that even with a high potential of natural gas, it is recommended to diversify the economy for sustainable growth. The use of natural gas as a fuel for gas turbines in two power stations in the KSA has been studied by [36], where

gas is recommended as a fuel for more power generation efficiency. [37] assessed the feasibility of underground gas storage (UGS) in the KSA, with multiple possibilities for importing liquified natural gas (LNG) and domestic gas usage taken into consideration. The findings show that imports of LNG would be more prudent in a situation with low gas production, whereas UGS and higher gas production result in a net benefit for the energy system. Despite the country's substantial natural gas reserves, using it for exports and revenue generation does not appear to be in Saudi Arabia's economic interest. Vision 2030, instead, aims to replace less efficient oil with the consumption of natural gas. However, the usage of gas must also be phased out in order to meet the 2060 net zero goal, or CO₂ emissions must be reduced using CCUS or DAC technologies.

Figure 2.6 Production and consumption of gas in the KSA [31].

c. Coal

Coal is generally not used for electricity generation due to the lack of sufficient reserves in the KSA⁶. Furthermore, coal is mostly consumed in cement production and is imported from countries such as South Africa, Indonesia, and Australia [38]. Even though these imports are considerably low, the consumption of coal has been increasing recently, and there has been concerns that Saudi Arabia is planning to increase the usage of coal, especially since The Saudi Petroleum Company signed a contract to establish the largest calcined coal production plant in the Middle East [39]. In 2016, due to increasing interest from countries in the region to utilize coal for electricity generation, a study on the potential of coal-fired power plants in Saudi Arabia was conducted [38]. The study concluded that electricity generation by coal cannot compete against the low prices of other fuels, especially in the long-term, and that the level of CO₂ emissions will become critical when coal-fired generation is used excessively [38]. The study focused on electricity generation by coal from an economic point of view, but neglected the

⁶<https://www.worldometers.info/coal/saudi-arabia-coal/>

environmental effects regarding higher emissions when burning coal. It is not advisable for a country that has never used coal for power generation to start doing so at a time when global efforts are attempting to phase out coal for energy usage because of its greater CO₂ intensity and its consequences on climate change. Thankfully, when Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 was unveiled in 2017, coal was not a consideration for producing electricity. This is further evidenced by the paucity of literature in the area, which demonstrates a lack of interest for coal use. However, given the massive expansion the nation is undergoing, the cement industry appears to be rapidly expanding, which is causing more coal to be burned and more emissions to be produced. Accordingly, the use of coal in the industry should be regulated in order to control its emissions.

2.2.2 Solar Energy

The average solar irradiation in Saudi Arabia is among the highest in the world. Its location in the earth's sunbelt, between latitudes 40°N and 40°S, where solar resources are abundant, is strategically valuable [40]. Consequently, solar energy has been of interest for research in Saudi Arabia since the mid-seventies [41], with recent rapid growth due to the country's plans to switch to renewables, where a substantial number of studies of solar energy potential in the KSA have been published. These studies range from small-scale solar energy installations in remote areas up to country scale solar potential. They also include integration of solar energy with other technologies. The focus will be on studies that consider country scale solar energy applications.

When assessing solar energy resources, it is critical to investigate the functionality of various solar radiation types. Global horizontal irradiance (GHI), direct normal irradiance (DNI), and diffusive horizontal irradiance (DHI) are the three forms of irradiance that are taken into account for solar energy harvesting [42]. The DHI relates to scattered solar radiation, which is frequently lower under clear sky conditions. DNI is the amount of solar energy that a surface, normally orientated to the sun's direct beams, receives per square meter of surface area. DNI, DHI, and ground-reflected radiation are added together to form GHI [42]. Contrary to concentrated solar thermal (CSP) technology, which operates by utilizing solely DNI sun irradiation, photovoltaic (PV) systems operate by accessing the availability of both DNI and DHI solar irradiation. To assess solar irradiation across the entire nation, Saudi Arabia has set up 46 solar measurement stations [43]. The average daily GHI and DNI during the years 2013 and 2018, according to data from the Saudi General Authority for Statistics, were found to be 5.9 and 5.6 kWh/m²/day, respectively [43]. Furthermore, a model has also been created by [44] to evaluate the averages of GHI and DNI in the Arabian Peninsula using data gathered between 1980 and 2017. The Arabian Peninsula is largely occupied by Saudi Arabia, circa 80%. Its findings indicate that: whereas the average annual DNI ranges from 3 to 6.5kWh/m² with considerable seasonal changes, the total average

annual GHI varies from 6 to 8.5kWh/m². Due to a higher average irradiance, as shown in **Figure 2.7**, some areas are more favourable for solar projects than others.

Figure 2.7 Long term average GHI, and DNI, period 1999-2018 [45].

When evaluating an area for the use of solar energy, there are additional aspects to consider. These include temperature, dust, and cloud cover, which have an impact on the effectiveness of solar technology [44]. [46] employed a GIS-AHP based approach to estimate the best possible location for a solar energy project, taking into consideration protected lands, major roads, slope, and urban areas. Results indicate that the most suitable places are in the north and northwest of the country, as depicted in **Figure 2.8**. These findings were also supported by [47], where the Tabuk region, in the northwest, was found to be the most feasible location for a solar energy project.

Figure 2.8 Most suitable areas for solar energy project [46]

Most studies on solar energy utilization in the KSA focus on the application of PV technology to produce electricity, with few papers on the application of CSP. [48], in their study of the progress of solar energy in the KSA, claimed that the best and least expensive way to provide essential energy services in the area is to use solar technologies, particularly PVs. However, [49] used an optimization model to study an all-solar electricity system. The study included three case studies: the first, a system of CSP and storage, the second, a PV with storage, and the third, PV and CSP with storage. The study concluded that a combination of PV, CSP and storage is the best option in terms of total system cost, storage requirements and energy spillage. **Table 2.1** shows the estimated system cost for each case of this study.

Table 2.1 Investment, operation, and total system costs for different cases [49].

	Investment (M\$)	Operation (M\$)	Total cost (M\$)
CSP & Storage	63,390	2245	65,635
PV & Storage	49,638	1220	50,858
CSP+PV & Storage	46,381	1345	47,726

Furthermore, [50] performed a simulation using RETScreen to analyze the potential of PV systems in 32 scattered locations across the country and compared the use of fixed tilt angle, 1-axis and 2-axis tracking modes. It was discovered that there is high energy production at locations in northern Saudi Arabia (Tabuk and Timma) due to low average temperatures, and locations in southern Saudi Arabia (Najran and Sharourah) due to high average sun irradiance. Additionally, the results revealed that the energy difference between 1-axis and 2-axis tracking is approximately 3.0-4.5%, while the difference between fixed mode and 1-axis tracking is between 28-33%. This signifies that from an economical perspective, Saudi Arabia does not need to use the 2-axis tracking mode. However, [51] using RETScreen, found that due to the maximum solar radiation intensity and longest sunlight duration, Bisha and Najran, southwest of the country, was determined as the optimal location for the development of a 10 MW installed capacity grid linked photovoltaic power plant. Whereas Sulayel, in the southern part, and Tabuk, are the poorest locations from the perspective of yearly energy output and economic aspects. This is contrary to what earlier research discovered regarding the Tabuk region's solar energy potential, most likely as a result of the study's inadequate assessment of solar radiation. [52] have attempted to calculate the levelized energy cost (LCOE) and PV area needed to meet the peak and baseload power demands of the entire nation, and to compare those figures to subsidized and unsubsidized costs of electricity in the Kingdom. Two model scenarios were considered using RETScreen: best case and worst-case scenarios. LCOE for the best and worst cases were found to be 0.0356 and 0.0463 USD/kWh, respectively. When comparing both cases to

the subsidized and unsubsidized LCOE, it was found that the LCOE for a peak load, met solely by solar energy, is significantly higher than the subsidized and unsubsidized LCOE, and that the area is not a limiting factor. There is a limitation to this study for not accounting for energy storage and its costs, while having a fully solar system, which will not be useful at nighttime. Furthermore, Saudi Arabia has plans on exporting electricity generated using solar power. [53] investigated the prospects of these plans for different countries in the world LCOE and the net present cost (NPC). It was found that several locations in Pakistan, India, and Turkey are economically feasible for solar energy exports, whereas locations in European countries were found to be unfeasible.

On the contrary, CSP systems are available in numerous forms and configurations, each with a unique set of features. However, few papers have compared the utility-scale performance of various CSP technologies and PV power generation. [54] used techno-economic and SWOT analysis to estimate the best technology option for the CSP project in Saudi Arabia, where six different scenarios were defined, and a simulation was performed using the System Advisor Model (SAM). The paper revealed that CSP among solar tower (ST), parabolic trough collectors (PTC) and Linear Fresnel Reflector (LFR) are the most developed for large-scale operations and are employed in the majority of active CSP projects. It was also concluded that there is a very high potential for CSP projects in Saudi Arabia. However, further research needs to be conducted due to ongoing developments and studies to incorporate CSP on a large-scale manner. Moreover, a lack of experience in the field poses a challenge as well as education and research, which play a major part in the development of CSP. The current low use of CSP in the KSA is mainly in cogeneration with other gas turbine power plants. [55] attempted to study this integration by carrying out a thermo-economic analysis for different configurations of CSP with gas turbine. The analysis evaluated the LCOE and carbon emissions generated by the usage of PTC, LFR or ST and demonstrated that integrating LFR with a gas turbine cogeneration plant's steam side is the ideal option. Other studies have compared the performance of CSP technologies against PV. Considering hourly meteorological data from 10 sites throughout the KSA and SAM software, and a variety of utility-scale CSP and PV, possible designs were investigated in [56] to discover which system would be the most effective. All forms of CSP were found to have capital costs higher than those of PV. However, as shown in **Figure 2.9**, the average LCOE for ST and PTC concentrated solar power was found to be lower than that of PV systems. The LCOE values, however, vary depending on region. Therefore, taking into account all 10 locations in [56], the analysis indicated that solar PV and PTC are desirable options in the Saudi energy market given their low LCOE. Another study compared PV systems with 4 and 9 hours of storage to PTC and ST CSP with 9 hours of storage plants in three different locations in Saudi Arabia [57]. A different modelling tool was used to evaluate the systems' efficiency. The findings indicate that relative to other technologies, PV with 9 hours of storage had the highest Annual Load Supply Factor (ALSF) and

highest LCOE. Furthermore, the results revealed that the plant with the lowest LCOE among those with ALSF greater than 0.5 was an ST with a 9-hour storage capacity. With a typical efficiency of around 20% for CSP systems, thermal losses in the Rankine cycle account for over 60% of energy losses. Another 20% of energy is lost through additional ancillary losses, primarily as heat in the circulating fluid and heat exchangers. Sceptics of PV technology in [58] have discussed that PV and the battery storage system is not the best alternative for the energy system in Saudi Arabia. Their claim is supported by a high frequency model (one minute or less) built for the Australian National Electricity Market grid to evaluate the renewables potential, since Australia publishes transparent data regarding renewable energy. The findings show that dramatic variability is seen at full grid level, and the amount of power generated from renewables at certain times is negligible. They suggested the growth of nuclear power plants may be more helpful to the economy and the environment. Moreover, PTC power plants along the coast have benefits over solar PV in terms of solar energy because thermal energy storage can provide the dispatchability needed. Finally, a centralized power plant also performs better than several rooftop photovoltaic systems. This study mirrored a model for Australia and reflected its findings on Saudi Arabia. The results of this study need to be further investigated as it argues against most of the literature concerning renewable energy, not only that related to the KSA.

Figure 2.9 LCOE values of utility-scale solar technologies in the KSA [56].

The literature shows a general interest in the solar energy applications in Saudi Arabia, where there is almost no dispute regarding its potential for the energy system. Therefore, the country is taking steps in exploiting this energy as part of its Vision 2030. Generally, the KSA is considering an ambitious goal to build utility scale PV projects to provide 40 GW of power to the country by 2030. PV was considered due to its maturity and long experience in the field. However, a few pilot CSP projects totalling approximately 2GW were also considered to test the viability of the technology in the country, as it still shows potential. The major advantage CSP has over PV is the ability to operate under high temperatures, which is a norm

in the Saudi Arabian climate. With ongoing development of CSP technology and finding the optimal configuration, it could become an ideal option for utilizing solar energy in the future. Despite the current plan, previous plans were made as [59] discussed in 2016, which is the Saudi Plan to achieve 24GW of its generation from solar energy by 2020. However, this goal is far from being met, which raises concerns about the commitment of the government on its plans.

2.2.3 Wind Energy

Although solar energy studies are dominant in research regarding renewable energy in Saudi Arabia, wind energy applications have become of great interest lately, with the number of studies growing rapidly. In the literature, wind energy potential in the KSA was evaluated on a country scale as well as small-scale in certain locations. The focus here will be on studies that covered the whole country or a large part of it. A short review was made by [60] that used data from 2007 to 2016 to estimate the potential of wind energy in the country. The results of the review show a potential of wind energy in several locations of the country where the wind speed is higher, as shown in **Figure 2.10**. It can be seen that northwest and southwest areas are of more potential for wind energy, along with locations in the central region. In 2018, [61] performed the first assessment of wind energy over the Arabian Peninsula, the MENA CORDEX (Middle East North Africa Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment) model output was used to examine the wind energy potential from a spatiotemporal perspective. It was found that the highest potential of wind energy is mostly across regions in the southeast, close to the Arabian (Persian) Gulf, and along the Red Sea coast. However, other places can also experience strong wind energy potential during particular seasons.

Figure 2.10 Average wind speed at 100m across Saudi Arabia [60].

It has been observed that there is a trend towards exploring the potential of wind power along the Red Sea coast, as shown in [62], [63] and [64]. [62] and [64] recommended Al-Wajh city, northwest of the country, for wind energy installation as it has the highest potential. Although [64] did not consider Al-Wajh in the study, it was shown that Haql city, north of Al-Wajh, is the best option. Both cities lie within the NEOM project, which encouraged [65] to study wind energy in that location. According to the paper's predicted wind power density (WPD), the NEOM location is classified as Class 3, which means wind energy facilities are acceptable for commercial operation. All of these previous studies used meteorological data from several scattered stations established by King Abdullah City for Atomic and Renewable energy (KA-CARE). Another paper covered two of the non-coastal cities for the installation of 15MW wind power plants in Saudi Arabia, Badanah in the north and Khamis-Mashayt in the southwest [66]. The analysis was conducted using NREL's HOMER software and found that at Badanah and Khamis-Mushayt, the 15 MW wind plants are expected to produce a considerable amount of electricity annually, 18,778 and 11,314 MWh, respectively. However, data used for this analysis is from the period 1970-1982, and this study was conducted in 2018. Therefore, the use of long-term recent data is recommended. Furthermore, a detailed assessment for wind farm development was conducted using GIS-based analysis, where [67] revealed that the most suitable sites for establishing a wind farm in Saudi Arabia include Ras Tanura on the eastern coast, and Al-Wajh and Turaif in the north. This evaluation was influenced by a range of climatic, economic, aesthetic, and environmental factors, including the availability of wind resources, road accessibility, safe distance from several settlements and airports, slope of the terrain, electrical grid proximity, and the impact on birds. In the author's opinion, [67] performed the best assessment of onshore wind energy installation in the literature so far. Nevertheless, there seems to be little interest for offshore wind energy in the KSA. Two papers have discussed the potential of offshore wind energy in Saudi Arabia: [68] covered the eastern coast, whereas [69] covered the western coast, specifically at the planned HVDC interconnection between Saudi Arabia and Egypt. Assessment in the east coast indicated that the annual energy yield generated from an offshore wind turbine was around 1.7 GWh, which is relatively lower than the other estimated onshore installation. However, the assessment of offshore wind installations carried out in the northwestern part showed a significantly higher amount of estimated energy yield (around 37 GWh) compared to the onshore estimated installations. Therefore, this system has major advantages in terms of annual energy yield as well as cost effectiveness and possible electricity exports in the future.

Wind energy has a high potential in some regions in Saudi Arabia and further research on its potential and development is recommended. Studies in the literature show that the northwestern part of Saudi Arabia is the most favourable for wind energy systems, which justifies the site selection of the NEOM project. Currently, only one wind energy project is under construction, the Dumat Al Jandal project, with

400MW capacity⁷. The KSA targets 16GW of wind energy as part of its Vision 2030. This goal is farfetched if the country's current pace of development continues, thus, major changes have to be considered and applied.

2.2.4 Other Renewables

In terms of potential and intentions for the future, the Saudi Arabian government has shown more interest in solar and wind energy. However, the potential of other renewable energy sources has been examined. The country's limited rainfall and lack of flowing rivers make it unattractive to use hydro electricity from waterways and bodies. Nevertheless, [70] made an interesting study of utilizing hydropower from residual pressure of water transmission pipelines by installing a Pelton turbine. The report found that power generated from this system reached almost 6MW, with a payback period of around 9.5 years, which shows a promising method of reducing energy losses in water transmission lines through hydropower application. Given that Saudi Arabia is one of the countries which produces the most desalinated water, the results of this study might be broadened and further investigated to include other water transmission lines that are already in place or being constructed⁸. In addition, marine energy applications on the Red Sea and Arabian/Persian Gulf coasts of the KSA were examined. [71] evaluated the potential of wave energy in different locations along the Red Sea coast with a high-resolution model using Advanced Weather Research Forecasting and WAVEWATCH III. Their research concluded that since the Red Sea's waves are too weak to operate the currently available wave energy converters, there are no potential locations for wave energy exploitation. The significant geographical and temporal variability of wave strength seen by [72] in the Red Sea may also be a contributing factor in low wave energy potential. The study did predict that Red Sea waves would become more powerful in the future. Initial work to test marine energy in the NEOM project was conducted by [73], using Advanced Research Weather and Forecasting model and WAVEWATCH III, with a better resolution than [71]. The results indicate that there is technical and social limitations when considering a wave energy installation in NEOM; further investigation by the authors is ongoing. Only one study was found in the literature that examined the marine energy potential in Saudi Arabia's shores of the Arabian/Persian Gulf [74]. The authors selected 8 locations for research, one of which was in Jubail, Saudi Arabia, while others were related to different countries. Unfortunately, it was shown that the power generated and the capacity factor at this site were the lowest compared to other parts of the Arabian/Persian Gulf. However, the fact that there is literature on the potential of wave energy in Saudi Arabia is a positive indication. The potential for tidal energy in the KSA, though, was not covered in any literature that was found. The

⁷<https://masdar.ae/en/Masdar-Clean-Energy/Projects/Dumat-Al-Jandal>

⁸<https://www.swpc.sa/en/water-transmission-capacity-plan/>

optimal solution for wave energy devices has not yet been discovered and they are still undergoing extensive development. According to research findings, hydropower harvesting in Saudi Arabia does not yet appear to be an attractive approach for the country's ambitious plans. Nonetheless, using hydro turbines to partially recover the energy lost in water transmission lines is an interesting concept. Further research is recommended for all applications of marine and hydro energy in Saudi Arabia.

Although research on the examination of geothermal resources in Saudi Arabia began in the 1980's, no significant geothermal projects have been implemented since that time. In 2009, [75] pointed out the potential of geothermal energy and investigated the obstacles facing its harvesting in the KSA. It was revealed that despite its appealing promise, the political backing for geothermal energy is low as a result of more affordable technologies being examined. Moreover, it was discussed that geothermal energy applications will generally not be considered in the near future. The study also suggested that increasing the awareness and education around geothermal energy might result in gaining more interest towards the subject. [76] reported in 2010 that Saudi Arabia is rich in a number of geological features such as 9 hot springs discovered in the southwestern districts of Jizan and Al Lith, with temperatures ranging from 39.5 to 79.5°C. This report classifies these springs as a low quality geothermal resource. The paper also expected that geothermal options will be considered in the near future, which is currently not the case. [77], [78] and [79] investigated the potential of geothermal energy in the regions of Jizan and Al Lith. The common findings are that there is low to medium potential of geothermal energy in these places suitable for a medium scale power plant or for using its heat in water desalination, thereby lowering the CO₂ emissions in both cases. Currently, it seems that there is no interest in utilizing geothermal energy in Saudi Arabia as it is not considered as part of the country's future plans for the energy mix. It is suggested that further research might lead to findings of appropriate geothermal applications that could contribute to the KSA's goal of reaching net zero.

The exploitation of biomass energy in Saudi Arabia has been of interest lately, especially in waste-to-energy (WTE) technologies. Municipal solid waste seems to be the largest contributor to the total waste in the Kingdom. The potential application of WTE has been studied in a number of papers. [80] covered this from energetic, economic, and environmental aspects by investigating various technologies of WTE. The results demonstrated that Saudi Arabia's yearly biomass waste production might be as much as 31.50 million tons, which could produce 15 TWh of energy annually. Despite having the largest costs of all the approaches examined, MSW incineration provides the most potential for electricity generation. Other types of biomass can be anaerobically digested, which has the benefit of small costs, minimal greenhouse gas emissions, and moderate energy production. [81] evaluated WTE application in the KSA and forecasted that if all of the organic waste is used in anaerobic digestion (AD) plants, an estimated 2.99 TWh of energy might be produced yearly. Similarly, if all of the plastics and other mixed waste are

treated using pyrolysis and refuse derived fuel (RDF) technologies, respectively, 1.03 and 1.55 TWh of energy can be generated annually. These figures appear more realistic since the data used is more accurate than in [80]. A financial model to research the feasibility of WTE facilities using gasification and AD WTE technologies has been established by [82]. The results indicate that from an economic perspective, the gasification plant has a better capacity for managing waste and producing electricity, and AD plants offer higher net present value (NPV) for investment. It is possible that the decision-makers favour gasification WTE facilities in densely populated areas. The attractiveness of AD plants increases with population density. However, both technologies show the potential of harvesting energy from biomass. Furthermore, [83] explored MSW WTE opportunities using different technologies. The study's findings indicate that when compared to RDF, and biomethanation and incineration with recycling scenarios, the incineration scenario has the most potential to generate power. However, it was also argued that the price of incineration is approximately 400 SAR per ton of waste, which is roughly 40 times more expensive than the price of the current landfill. Another paper compared the future energetic aspects to using WTE systems for energy generation in 6 different locations in the KSA through two scenarios, Mass Burn and Mass Burn with recycling [84]. It was found that by the year 2032, the former scenario is expected to generate about 18.5 TWh of energy annually, whereas the latter would only generate approximately 1.5 TWh annually. Both numbers are unattractive from economic and energetic perspectives. Nevertheless, for all WTE technologies, the environmental aspect seems to be the driver in adopting them, as the amount of waste in the Kingdom is increasing rapidly because of undergoing development and a rising population. Although biomass is considered as a renewable resource, it is not fully regarded as an environmentally friendly one, as some of its technologies still produce CO₂ and other toxic emissions⁹. Currently, there are no apparent plans to adopt WTE technologies; this is largely due to the lack of knowledge and infrastructure, as the country's vast desert land provides a cheap solution as landfill for waste, although this might not last for much longer.

2.2.5 Nuclear Energy

Development of nuclear energy in Saudi Arabia has been a disputed topic in the last decade, especially with the establishment of KACARE in 2010. However, only a few studies have covered the potential of nuclear energy in the KSA. [85] performed an economic comparative study between using nuclear energy, solar, and gas for electricity generation. The study concluded that nuclear energy is not economically feasible for power generation, and a combination of solar and gas is a better option. Moreover, the paper stated that the interest in nuclear energy is not an economical decision, but a political

⁹<https://www.eia.gov/energyexplained/biomass/biomass-and-the-environment.php>

one. [86] used a cost optimization model to develop a strategy for the adoption of nuclear power in Saudi Arabia. The model was created using MESAAGE tool, and data was acquired from KAPSARC. The results of this model forecast that the most viable future approach to meet Saudi Arabia's electricity needs by 2050 will be to embrace a combination of renewables, advanced traditional power, and nuclear technologies, with a capacity of 43.7%, 41.6%, and 3.8%, respectively. The adoption of nuclear power will certainly decrease CO₂ emissions, but the capacity of traditional power suggested in the study is still high if the country wants to go forward with the net zero goal, unless greater infrastructure for CCUS is considered. In addition to these studies, [87] employed a GIS-based multicriteria analysis to evaluate potential sites for nuclear energy plants. The study concluded that only 2% of the land in Saudi Arabia is suitable for nuclear energy plants, which is located on the coastlines of the Red Sea and the Gulf. The study also found that a major factor in deciding potential sites is water scarcity, as water is vital for nuclear energy generation. Part of the Vision 2030 plan is to utilize nuclear energy and build appropriate plants. However, a specific percentage of the planned capacities for nuclear energy has not been mentioned. Serious steps are being taken towards that goal, especially with the establishment of the Nuclear Holding Company this year. Although there has been much discussion around the safety of nuclear energy around the world, it is still an attractive option in terms of energy security.

2.2.6 Power System

Due to the high amount of oil and gas reserves in the Kingdom, electricity generation sources have shifted between oil and gas since the 1980's, as shown in **Figure 2.11**. The current percentages of electricity generation sources are approximately 61%, 38.5% and 0.5% for gas, oil, and solar electricity generation, respectively.

Figure 2.11 Share of electricity production by source¹⁰.

¹⁰<https://ourworldindata.org/energy/country/saudi-arabia>

Currently, there is no usage of coal or nuclear energy to produce electricity. A few solar installations produce an insignificant amount of electricity. Therefore, almost all of the electricity generated in the KSA is from thermal sources (i.e., oil and gas). From a technological standpoint, electricity in the KSA is generated using various types of technology, including diesel engines (DE), combined cycle gas turbines (CCGT), open cycle gas turbines (OCGT), and steam turbines. OCGT accounts for more than half of the system's units, although most need to be replaced because they are outdated and inefficient. For many years, efficiency has not been a major consideration in decision-making due to the structure of the KSA economy and extremely affordable fuel. According to the latest report from the WERA in Saudi Arabia [88], steam turbines and OCGT seem to be dominating in electricity generation, as shown in **Figure 2.12**. The author was unable to find any published studies that covered the conditions and performance of the current power plants, which is a gap that needs exploring since the country is planning to continue their use until 2030.

Figure 2.12 Available capacity by type of technology, refabricated from [88].

Saudi Arabia has a vast area of land, which is a major challenge for the power network. The high voltage (230 and 380 kV) transmission lines add up to just above 43 thousand circuit kilometers [88]. The Saudi Electricity company is the owner and operator of all transmission and distribution lines. **Figure 2.13** shows the length of the transmission lines by voltage. The percentages of underground transmission and distribution lines are 10% and 53%, respectively. It is difficult to transmit electricity throughout Saudi Arabia due to the great distances between its major cities, which are separated by vast, uninhabited regions with the exception of a few small, dispersed settlements. Line losses at transmission and distribution levels reached 7% in 2014, according to the Worldbank¹¹, which is relatively high compared

¹¹<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/EG.ELC.LOSS.ZS?locations=SA>

to best practice. In 2001, the GCC Countries, including Saudi Arabia, decided to create the GCC Interconnection Authority (GCCIA) in order to connect their respective electricity grids¹². The construction of the interconnection project started in 2005 and finished in 2009, connecting Saudi Arabia to Kuwait, Bahrain, Qatar, and UAE with capacities of 1,200, 600, 750, and 900 MW, respectively. In addition, UAE was connected to Oman with a capacity of 400 MW, as depicted in **Figure 2.14**. Iraq was excluded from this interconnection project. However, in July 2022, Saudi Arabia and Iraq agreed to

Figure 2.13 Length of transmission lines by voltage [88].

establish a 1,000 MW, 400 kV interconnection transmission line, and include it as part of the GCCIA network¹³. Furthermore, a contract for constructing an interconnection between Saudi Arabia and Egypt was awarded last year, with a 3,000 MW HVDC transmission line¹⁴. In the author's best knowledge, there are no HVDC lines currently operating in Saudi Arabia. Nonetheless, it is part of the country's plan to upgrade the infrastructure for its grid. One study was found that evaluated adopting HVDC, 500 kV AC and 725 kV AC into the power network for base cases of 2020, 2024 and 2030 [89]. The study analyzed generation scenarios from various regions and the lines required. It was revealed that the originally planned 380 kVAC transmission lines are adequate enough to provide necessary power transfer for the base generation scenario put forth by SEC, which focuses on generation being close to load centres. In this case, there would be no justifiable need for further HVDC lines or greater transmission voltage levels of AC. Whereas, for generation scenarios on the east and west coasts, the use of a 725 kV AC transmission line was recommended as it is the most cost-effective option. The third scenario is the renewable generation in the northwest region (NEOM' location), where establishing a ± 600 kV HVDC to

¹²https://www.gccia.com.sa/P/phase_i/56

¹³<https://www.enerdata.net/publications/daily-energy-news/saudi-arabia-and-iraq-agree-1-gw-400-kv-power-transmission-line.html>

¹⁴<https://www.hitachienergy.com/uk-ie/en/news/press-releases/2021/10/hitachi-abb-power-grids-consortium-awarded-major-contract-for-the-first-ever-large-scale-hvdc-interconnection-in-the-middle-east-and-north-africa>

transfer power to the central region would be suitable. The power network in Saudi Arabia has been sufficient for the country for a long time, especially with low fuel prices. However, the significant development the country is going through, and the increase in population will require an enormous upgrading of the grid's infrastructure.

Figure 2.14 Map of interconnection network of GCCIA.

Many factors affect the electricity demand in Saudi Arabia. Major factors include the population growth and the economic development of the country, which are variable based on regions [90]. For many years, the electricity consumption in residential buildings has been the highest compared to other categories, with around 50% of the demand. **Figure 2.15** shows the electricity consumption by category. Consequently, more interest in lowering this consumption has been growing. Most of it is due to cooling by the use of Air Conditioning on hot summer days, which consumes a large quantity of electricity. Therefore, the peak load in the country is usually at noon in the summer, as shown in **Figure 2.16**. Accordingly, [91] explored the factors that influence household electricity demand in the nations of the GCC by using the structural time series model. The model considers population, weather, and an energy demand trend, in addition to the economic variables of GDP and actual electricity prices. The findings of the study imply that in order to reduce domestic energy usage, regional governments would need to promote consumer knowledge of energy use and enhance appliances efficiency, perhaps through advertising and education efforts. Furthermore, it was suggested that even if prices were raised, the impact on reducing residential electricity growth in the region is likely to be minimal unless, prices were raised so high that electricity expenditure became a large portion of income. Another study projected Saudi Arabia's sectoral electricity consumption up to 2030 using a computable general equilibrium model [92]. In comparison to historical trends, it was predicted that during the next ten years, the rise of the overall Saudi electricity demand will drastically slow down due to government policies on increasing

efficiency and introducing a higher tariff. Up to 71.6 TWh less electricity will be consumed globally in 2030 if Saudi Arabia's electricity costs are brought into line with the G20 average. Up to 118.7 TWh can be cut from the overall electricity demand by independently executing efficiency rules. Furthermore, according to the paper's base case, by 2030 the demand will have grown to 365.4 TWh. The study stated that the sectoral segmentation reveals significant differences between sectors, where the industrial and services sectors are expected to see faster growth in demand than the residential market. However, it was confirmed that the latter will continue to represent the greatest portion of total consumption in 2030.

Demand side management (DSM) is a new approach that has been discussed lately. Unfortunately, few studies have covered the application of DSM techniques in Saudi Arabia. [93] developed a tariff structure for residential demand that will encourage consumers to shift the load to the off-peak time in order to avoid a higher tariff. The suggested structure is based on a simple model and analysis, thus, it requires improvements to accommodate the whole network in all categories. Currently, the installed generation capacity exceeds the demand. However, this might not be the case in the future with a rapid increase in demand. There are no official plans to deploy DSM for the electricity grid, and the main goal of Vision 2030 regarding this matter is to increase and diversify generation to meet demand.

Figure 2.15 . Electricity consumption by category [88].

Figure 2.16 Electricity load variation for the year 2015 in Saudi Arabia [49].

There are only a few players in the electricity market of Saudi Arabia. The largest of which are SEC, MARAFIQ, Hajr, Saline Water Conversion Corporation (SWCC) and other independent generators. The transmission network is owned solely by SEC, and all other generators sell electricity to this company. The electricity tariff is controlled by SEC, since it sells electricity directly to consumers. Although SEC represents itself as a private company, it is highly influenced by the government. Recommendations to break this monopoly and promote a competitive market were made in 2008 [94], and Saudi Arabia has started taking steps in that direction. However, not many studies have discussed a framework for a competitive market, mostly due to the government influence over SEC. [95] studied the impact of PV plants' involvement in various market structures in the Saudi power grid. The market schemes that were evaluated are Marginal Pricing (MP) and Pay-as-Bid (PAB), both compared in an adjustment market (AM) as well as a day ahead market (DA). The paper found that the MP-DA plan is the ideal scheme for solar plants since it encourages their construction in congested locations and allows them to generate more profit. The MP-DA program also provides the highest level of social benefit. The MP-AM scheme has the largest consumer surplus among the schemes that manage AM congestion, which is favourable for consumers in the short term but will delay the building of new power plants. On the contrary, feed-in-tariffs (FIT) are not implemented in the current market. [96] and [97] analyzed FIT application and policies from Europe, the United States and other countries, in order to develop a similar system for Saudi Arabia. [96] followed a numerical approach to estimate the FIT for PV development. The calculation resulted in an average FIT of 0.08SAR/kWh across the whole country, with a return of investment of seven to nine years depending on the region. This value is relatively low compared to the current tariff of 0.18 SAR/kWh. Consequently, the study stated that FIT is still not an attractive option for the Saudi

electricity market. However, as the costs for PV technology is decreasing every year, FIT might present itself as an optimal solution in the future. [97] followed a descriptive approach in evaluating FIT implementation in Saudi Arabia and recommended its use as it has performed well in other countries. In terms of international trading of electricity with the GCC countries, it is managed by GCCIA and there are hardly any published details available. There is no dispute that the electricity market in the KSA is immature compared to the developed world. Many changes and improvements should be considered if the country wants to fulfil its plans for Vision 2030 and further.

2.2.7 Storage, Hydrogen and Carbon Capture

Wind, solar, and other weather-based renewable energy sources are by their very nature inconsistent and temperamental. Electricity storage devices with multiple MW capacities and several hours of length are essential if renewable energy is to become a significant source of power. [98] performed a techno-economic analysis to test the application of various energy storage types for renewables in the KSA. The storage systems evaluated include pumped storage hydro (PSH), compressed air energy storage (CAES), flywheel, capacitors/supercapacitors, superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES), lead-acid battery, vanadium redox batteries (VRB), zinc bromine batteries (ZRB), polysulphide bromide (PSB), Nickel cadmium battery, Li-ion, Metal-air, and sodium sulphur batteries. The study concluded that among the concepts discussed, VRB and sodium sulphur batteries appear to have the greatest potential for use in renewable energy applications, with recommendation of additional research. [99] used computational analysis to build a model of solar PV panels, in integration with Li-ion batteries, or flow batteries. Results of the model indicate that Li-ion batteries were found to be the optimum alternative for energy storage in the KSA metrological environment. The potential of PSH in Saudi Arabia has been evaluated by [100]. It was revealed that PSH is not economically feasible in the current market structure. However, PSH can be encouraged by introducing ancillary services to the market. [101] analyzed the possible techno-economic viability of hybrid renewable energy systems (HRES) with storage based on pumped hydro, batteries, and hydrogen, for a small town at Sharurah in the southern region of Saudi Arabia. Sharurah is one of the best locations for PV and wind installations. For the analysis, three storage alternatives: battery banks, pumped hydro, and hydrogen storage units were taken into account. NPC, LCOE, renewable fraction (RF), and environmental effect were the evaluation parameters used to analyze the performance of different HRES scenarios. The analysis was performed using HOMER software. According to the findings, the PV-diesel-battery HRES is the best option and has a minimum NPC of \$2.70 million and LCOE of \$0.178/kWh. Another study used HOMER software to find the optimum layout for a HRES microgrid and hydrogen storage facility in Yanbu city, northwest of Saudi Arabia [102]. Several configurations have been tested with findings demonstrating that a hybrid PV-wind-

battery-generator microgrid with a NPC and LCOE cost of \$10.6 billion and \$0.15/kWh is the best configuration for the targeted area. This configuration is estimated to generate approximately 32,132 tons of hydrogen annually and avoid 380,824t CO₂/year. Evaluating these results, the paper concluded that building electrolyzers in regions with high quality renewable resource conditions, such as Saudi Arabia, might become a low-cost hydrogen supply alternative as PV and wind generation costs decrease. In Saudi Arabia, the fields of energy storage and hydrogen generation are expanding, and further research and development is being conducted in these areas. As part of its development, the KSA announced the establishment of the world's largest battery storage facility, with 1,000 MWh capacity¹⁵. The storage unit will be powered by PV and wind energy to provide continuous supply to the Red Sea project. Furthermore, Saudi Arabia is developing a strategy to become one of the leading countries in hydrogen production through renewable energy [103].

CCUS is a new field of discussion in literature pertaining to Saudi Arabia. In 2012, CCUS in the KSA was discussed for the first time, where the potential of carbon capture implementation is mentioned [104]. The paper recommended that policymakers established policies for CCUS in order to reduce emissions. This recommendation was also supported by the findings of [105]. [106] performed an overview of the optimal reservoirs for carbon capture and storage (CCS) as well as enhanced oil recovery (EOR) applications. The results revealed that in the non-hydrocarbon-prolific sector, the Kharij, Az-Zulfi, Layla, and Wasia aquifers have been recommended as CCS candidates. Whereas, for EOR, Safaniya, Manifa, and Khuff oil fields have been suggested as the best candidates. Findings of this paper indicate a high potential of CCS in Saudi Arabia, along with the benefits of using the captured CO₂ in EOR, where it showed promising results in [107]. The first injection of CO₂ in Saudi Arabia commenced in 2015. CCS-EOR was applied by Saudi Aramco in the Uthmaniyah oil reservoir¹⁶. At the facility in Hawiyah, Aramco has the capacity to gather and process around 2,500t CO₂ every day. The captured CO₂ is transported 85 km by pipe and pushed into the oil reservoir, where it is sequestered and helps to increase oil recovery and maintain reservoir pressure. Moreover, there is ongoing research at Aramco to develop mobile CCS for cars and trucks, with a proposed initial technology that can harness up to 25% of vehicle emissions. This research is interesting as it lowers CO₂ emissions from the transport sector. Saudi Arabia is also planning to establish a fund to boost carbon capture and support a scheme to develop clean fuels for cooking. The combined cost of the two projects is 39 billion riyals (\$10.4 billion), of which Saudi Arabia would bear 15% [108]. There is great interest in CCUS technologies in Saudi Arabia as it has one of the

¹⁵<https://www.theredsea.sa/en/newsroom/worlds-largest-battery-storage-facility-will-power-the-red-sea-project-with-clean-energy-247#>

¹⁶<https://www.aramco.com/en/sustainability/climate-change/managing-our-footprint/carbon-capture-utilization-and-storage>

largest oil and gas reservoir. These policies indicate that the country would not phase out the use of fossil fuels anytime soon, instead it would reduce the emissions by CCUS. Research and development in the field are rapidly growing, especially after the announcement of the net zero target.

2.3 Summary

This chapter discussed energy modelling and tools that have been developed for energy system modelling including PyPSA. Features of PyPSA in comparison to other tools were explored and PyPSA was favoured for this thesis mostly due to its availability and active support. The chapter also reviewed studies that covered the energy system in Saudi Arabia, particularly from different sectors and energy generation technologies. Fossil fuels (i.e., oil, gas, and coal), solar, wind and other renewables have been discussed, as well as the electricity sector, storage and carbon capture technologies. The literature on Saudi Arabia is not mature enough and there are many gaps that were identified which have the potential for exploring. Furthermore, it appears that the majority of the literature published after Vision 2030 was announced agrees with the plan's objectives, which may or may not be a positive indication.

Chapter 3: Methods

This chapter discusses the procedures used to create this thesis in order to accomplish its objectives as stated in Section 1.2. The main objective of this thesis is to develop a model for the power system in Saudi Arabia that represent its net zero target in 2060. Various model scenarios have been built which represent the potential status of power demand in 2060. In addition, a different scenario is created to include direct air capture of CO₂ and evaluate the optimization in the event that the KSA decides to continue using fossil fuels to generate power. A model of the base network was also developed for validation as well as a model for the KSA's 2030 power network as a transition phase, in order to compare it with the country's Vision 2030. Finally, suggestions are made for the energy system of 2060.

The PyPSA-Africa (v0.0.2) package has been used to establish these models of the network. As mentioned in Section 2.1.2, PyPSA-Africa uses several work packages to generate models of some of the country's current characteristics using open data sources. These models include demand, conventional generators, available RES, land cover constraints, and networks and substations. In addition to these models, some data are used as a direct input to PyPSA-Africa, such as data that represent cost assumptions of various technologies. There are many options for contrasting scenarios that can then be modified in a configuration file. They include spatial and temporal resolutions, types of generators to include, CO₂ limit, and others. The models from the work packages as well as the costs are used as inputs to build the network model through configuration options. The network is then solved and optimized using one of the solvers. Gurubi is the solver used for this thesis due to its low computational time compared to others.

Figure 3.1 General overview of the methods followed.

Several scenarios are considered: three scenarios that represent different electricity demand values for 2060 and another scenario that includes DAC to test the system with carbon capture technology, in addition to the base and 2030 scenarios. Furthermore, as part of this work, data related to the work packages have been collected manually from official sources of the country for the sake of setting up the scenarios as well as validation of the work packages' models by PyPSA-Africa. Accordingly, the methods followed in this thesis include data collection, modelling, results representation, and validation. **Figure 3.1** illustrates a general overview of the methods followed in this thesis.

The organization of this chapter is as follows: Limitations to the followed methods were addressed in Section 3.1. The procedures in data collection both manually and through the PyPSA-Africa package are discussed in Section 3.2. Different configurations, set for the scenarios, are explained in Section 3.3. Validation of work packages' models and results representation methods are presented in Section 3.4.

3.1 Limitations

The proportion of literature related to the energy system in Saudi Arabia is relatively low compared to other developed countries, which proved to be a major limitation in data collection. Moreover, most of the data have been used in previous literature as well as the data acquired by the PyPSA-Africa package through open data sources taken from the Electricity & Co-Generation Regulatory Authority (ECRA). ECRA was discontinued and reformed into WERA in 2020 including its website (ecra.gov.sa), which had several data pages that were lost after the reformation. The data in these pages show detailed information about the electricity system, compared to the limited data available on WERA's website. Fortunately, part of the data from ECRA was recorded in some open datahubs used by PyPSA-Africa, thus, the data was retrieved. Currently, obtaining specific information regarding the electricity grid requires contacting WERA or other private organizations such as SEC, which was not beneficial for this thesis. Moreover, due to this limitation in data collection, costs for different technologies were taken as per the default assumptions in PyPSA-Africa, which were collected from many published credible sources¹⁷. These costs were then projected to 2060.

3.2 Data Collection

Databases, publications, reports, and public websites have all been used to collect data. Some of the information is displayed graphically rather than as numerical values. PyPSA-Africa also allows direct downloading of some of the previously collected data such as administrative country shapes, specific potential of renewable sources, OpenStreetMap data, population, GDP, etc.

¹⁷<https://github.com/pypsa-meets-africa/pypsa-africa/blob/main/data/costs.csv>

3.2.1 PyPSA-Africa Work Packages

As mentioned in Section 2.1.2, PyPSA-Africa uses several work packages to create models which are used as input to the optimization problem; these models can then be validated in comparison to the collected data. The work packages will be briefly explained with more emphasis on the demand modelling work package since several scenarios with different demands are considered.

a. Demand modelling

The hourly time series demand of Saudi Arabia is obtained through PyPSA-Africa using GlobalEnergyGIS (GEGIS) in order to model the use of electricity. This time series is based on historical power demand time series data, population densities, and spatially resolved income data. GEGIS employs a machine learning (ML) technique to produce hourly outputs for arbitrary locations up until 2050 [109]. GEGIS demands modelling works by using an hourly power demand time series for 44 nations from [110], a demand time series for each country was adjusted to the annual mean and fitted with a gradient boosting regression model. Estimates of the yearly country-level generation of energy in 2050 were obtained by projecting the annual demand in 2016 using the SSP2-34 scenario's growth in regional demand. In light of an independently determined mean, the machine learning approach produces predictions of annual and hourly load curves [109]. The machine learning model for GEGIS is trained on ten independent variables:

1. Annual per capita electricity use,
2. GDP adjusted for purchase power,
3. Yearlong average hourly temperature profiles for the three most populous regions of each country,
4. The annual mean temperature,
5. The year's first percentile of temperature,
6. The 99th percentile for temperature,
7. The hour of the day,
8. A weekend/weekday indication,
9. Average monthly temperatures,
10. A ranking of the months of the year based on temperature.

Finally, the synthetic demand model's ability to replicate load curve demand patterns on an hourly, daily, and seasonal time scale was validated by [109]. Using cross validation, data from the other 43 nations were exclusively used to fit the model for each of the 44 countries. One of these validated countries is Saudi Arabia, as shown in **Figure 3.2** The usage of many variables to model the demand in GEGIS produces relatively accurate results, which made it favourable for PyPSA-Africa.

Figure 3.2 Cross-validated model predictions (red) compared to real series (blue), for the year 2018 [109].

b. Existing generators modelling

Data is made accessible for the modelling of current powerplants through the Global Power Plant Database (GPPD), one of the main open global power plant databases¹⁸. The power plants' data for Saudi Arabia were collected from the ECRA website by GPPD, which is no longer in operation. Furthermore, PyPSA-Africa uses the powerplantmatching¹⁹ tool to integrate the power plants database with other databases.

c. RES modelling

The potential of renewable energy sources and their time series is estimated through Atlite [111], which is a python package specifically developed for this purpose. Atlite is an open-source Python software package for obtaining meteorological data from around the world such as wind speed and solar irradiation, and transforming it into time series and potentials for renewable generation of Solar PV and wind turbines using mathematical models. These potentials are represented in a grid of 30 km x 30 km cutouts, generated by Atlite using the recommended ER5 module.

d. Power network and substations

The World Bank Group's dataset, which was generated based on a variety of sources, will primarily be used to extract the topology of the network. An alternative is OpenStreetMap (OSM), but it may need

¹⁸<https://datasets.wri.org/dataset/globalpowerplantdatabase>

¹⁹<https://github.com/PyPSA/powerplantmatching>

additional data filtering to be functional. Physical information of the power network is provided by the voltage level and number of lines in both datasets. OSM may also be used to extract information on the locations and voltage levels of substations. A consistent network format is then created after gathering the substation and line data by some of the scripts of PyPSA-Africa.

e. Land coverage constraint modelling

The locations that are eligible for RES development, transmission line deployment, etc., are constrained by various land uses, difficult terrain, and protected regions. Atlite can incorporate both land- and sea-based restrictions. Moreover, water depth is a limitation for offshore and ocean energy applications in addition to oceanic climate considerations, and bathymetric data can be taken from the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO). Additionally, national reserves and other protected sites and their effect on the model will be discussed.

3.2.2 Time Series Electricity Demand

A collection of time series demand is conducted for the purpose of validation of the time series demand generated by PyPSA-Africa. Many studies in the literature used data of the time series demand obtained from ECRA's website. However, these studies only obtained the results from the data and did not show the actual time series data. Currently, official data for the time series demand of Saudi Arabia were not found publicly. However, weekly load distribution for the years 2019-2021 has been provided on WERA's website, as shown in **Figure 3.3**. Therefore, the weekly distribution for 2021 was taken and interpolated with the time series demand for Egypt, and Arizona, USA, which have similar weather to the KSA. Data for the time series demand of Egypt are obtained from PyPSA-Africa itself, whereas for Arizona, data are collected from EIA's open data Excel Add-in²⁰. Both interpolations result in a similar time series demand distribution for Saudi Arabia, as shown in **Figure 3.4**.

Figure 3.3 Saudi Arabia's weekly electricity demand distribution for the years 2019-2021²¹.

²⁰<https://www.eia.gov/odata/>

²¹<https://wera.gov.sa/Statistics/NRDetailsC1?CategoryId=7&SheetsId=7>

Figure 3.4 Timeseries electricity demand for Saudi Arabia compared to Egypt, and Arizona, USA.

3.2.3 Available RES and Land Cover Constraints

PyPSA-Africa estimates the potential of renewable energy through building a spatial distribution of average solar irradiance and wind speeds over the country. However, protected areas and land constraints limit the applications of renewable energy technologies. Therefore, PyPSA-Africa estimates the available renewable profiles by taking land constraints into consideration, then an assumption of certain renewable equipment, namely Vistas V112 for wind energy, and CSI PV for solar energy.

Public information was sought concerning Saudi Arabia's protected areas. The topology of the KSA is generally a desert with scarce vegetation. However, there are some protected lands that were established for small areas of vegetation that help in controlling erosion of soil and lowering dust occurrence, as well as protecting some of the endangered animals. **Figure 3.5** shows the natural reserves which were estimated by [46] as well as the protected lands that were officially announced as royal reserves by the government. **Figure 3.6** was obtained from the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA), which supports the estimation of [46]. These protected areas represent about 10-15% of the country's total area.

Figure 3.5 Protected lands in Saudi Arabia: (a) Estimated by [46], (b) Royal reserves [112].

Figure 3.6 Protected lands in Saudi Arabia, retrieved from WDPA²²

3.2.4 Existing Generators and Power network

KAPSARC, through their datahub, has provided data on power plants in Saudi Arabia²³. However, the number of power plants as well as their total capacity vary significantly from those mentioned in WERA's reports [88]. Moreover, the data on the website are not clearly referenced. The report mainly covered the number of power plants regarding the capacity for each subscriber, but not the specifics for each power plant. As of 2020, there are 84 power plants in the KSA with a total capacity of 90,043 MW according to WERA. Considering the power network, unfortunately, specific data for all the transmission lines and substations from official sources were not available, other than the lengths of lines by voltages shown in **Figure 2.13**. Nevertheless, the most recent official general overview of the transmission

²²https://resourcewatch.org/data/explore/bio007-World-Database-on-Protected-Areas_replacement

²³<https://datasource.kapsarc.org/explore/dataset/saudi-arabia-powerplants-output-co2-and-intensity/table/>

network was obtained from the SEC report of 2007 [113]. A more recent illustration was generated by [46] in 2017. **Figure 3.7** shows both networks.

Figure 3.7 Transmission network illustration in Saudi Arabia: (a) retrieved from [113], (b) generated by [46].

3.2.5 Costs

The costs in PyPSA-Africa are not limited to financial values, they also include technical values. Examples include²⁴ discount rate, lifetime, investment (CAPEX), fixed operation and maintenance (FOM), variable operation and maintenance (VOM), fuel costs, efficiency, and carbon-dioxide intensity. These values were collected from various global databases and sources, and were used as a direct input to the optimization problem. The default cost assumptions in PyPSA-Africa were used to generate the model for 2030 since they are generated for that year. In addition, two values were added to these costs that are relevant when applying DAC technology: the first is “electricity-input” and the second is “compression-electricity-input”, both obtained from PyPSA²⁵. Regarding 2060, the costs generated through PyPSA for the years 2020, 2025, 2030, 2035, 2040, 2045 and 2050, were calculated and forecasted using the FORECAST.ETS and FORECAST.LINEAR functions in Excel, where the former generated a more accurate forecast. This forecast was then used to interpolate the 2030 cost assumptions of PyPSA-Africa for 2060 to generate the 2060 model. The cost assumptions used for both 2030 and 2060 are listed in Appendix B.

3.3 Network Modelling

Most of the options for network modelling can be found in the configuration file. The default file was used for modelling in this thesis, but with some modifications. The main modification being the selection

²⁴<https://github.com/pypsa-meets-africa/pypsa-africa/blob/main/doc/costs.rst>

²⁵<https://github.com/PyPSA/technology-data>

of Saudi Arabia with ISO code “SA” instead of the default “Africa”. Furthermore, all the scenarios are based on line expansion being optimized according to its capital cost with the “lcopt” wildcard. Additionally, battery and hydrogen storages were considered as extendable for all models. Other options are discussed in further sections. When testing the models, nuclear energy did not show any potential as an extendable carrier for either 2030 or 2060. Therefore, it was not considered in the final models. The script of the configuration file for various scenarios is shown in Appendix C.1.

3.3.1 Spaciotemporal resolutions

PyPSA-Africa can be used for high spatial and temporal resolutions. Higher resolutions will lead to higher computation time and, thereby, provide more accurate results. Spatial resolution is defined by the number of clusters in the configuration file. Different numbers have been used and tested to find an optimal value with a reasonable computation time and acceptable results. The first value was four clusters, due to the country having four power operating areas, as shown in **Figure 3.7(a)**. The second value was thirteen, which represents the number of administrative regions in the KSA. A higher resolution of thirty and sixty clusters were then chosen. From all spatial resolutions, the thirty clusters option was chosen for all different scenarios due to coverage of most of the country as well as reasonable computation time. **Figure 3.8** shows the different spatial resolutions that were tested and how they cover the country. As for time resolution, an hourly time resolution resulted in a reasonable computation time, with a full year of snapshots. Moreover, the weather year used was the default 2013 due to available data for Saudi Arabia.

Figure 3.8 Spatial resolutions (from left) of 4, 13, 30 and 60 clusters.

3.3.2 Scenario of base network

The default settings of PyPSA-Africa predict the electricity demand for 2030. However, a scaling factor could be used in the configuration file under “load_options” to scale the load to another estimated value. Therefore, the current network was modelled by taking the value of the current annual load and relating it to the prediction year of 2030 to find the most appropriate scale. The scale value for this model

was found to be approximately 0.673. Moreover, the generation capacity was limited to the current conventional carriers without extending other generators. This is performed by setting “estimate_renewable_capacities>p_nom_max” value to 1.0, and eliminating the options under “extendable_carriers> Generator” in the configuration file. Furthermore, the CO₂ limit was not considered in the scenario for this model.

3.3.3 Scenario of 2030

The default settings of PyPSA-Africa are set for modelling the networks for 2030, in addition to the cost assumptions. Consequently, as a first step for the country’s goals, a 2030 model was considered and modelled. Modelling with PyPSA-Africa provides the option to set an overall absolute carbon-dioxide emissions limit. The base emissions were taken as an average of five years from 2014-2019, resulting in a value of around 542 mtpa of emissions [5]. As part of SGI, the KSA plans to reduce its annual emissions to 278 mtpa, almost half of its current emissions. This value was considered as the CO₂ limit in modelling for 2030, as well as extending the capacity of gas and renewable generation, with phasing out oil as a generator, as per the Vision 2030 goals. This was implemented through setting “estimate_renewable_capacities> p_nom_max” to False as well as adding “[OCGT, CCGT]” in “extendable_carriers> Generator”. The demand value for this model was taken as the default prediction of PyPSA-Africa for 2030.

3.3.4 Scenarios of 2060

It is necessary to make several assumptions in order to simulate the network for 2060. First are the cost assumptions discussed in Section 3.2.5. Second is the electricity demand for 2060, since PyPSA-Africa estimates demand using GEGIS for certain prediction years, namely 2030, 2040, 2050 and 2100. The demand forecasts in the literature are limited to 2030 and do not account for the mega projects that the country is considering. Therefore, in order to predict demand for 2060, demand models for 2030, 2040 and 2050 have been generated through PyPSA-Africa. The values of the resulting estimated demand from these models are almost linear, although demand forecasting is usually not. For the purpose of simplicity in this thesis, and as demand forecasting is out of its scope, a linear regression through Excel was performed from the estimated demand models to provide a value for the demand in 2060. Nevertheless, models with a percentage of $\pm 15\%$ from this forecasted demand value were considered in order to perform a sensitivity analysis with changing demand values. **Figure 3.9** illustrates the linear relationship of the demand models as well as the demand forecasts for 2060. The scale value is multiplied by the time series demand which PyPSA-Africa generates to estimate different demand scenarios. The approximated scale for 2060 is found to be 1.25 from the prediction year 2050 for the main 2060 scenario. For the other

scenarios, with $\pm 15\%$ from the main scenario, the scale values become 1.1 and 1.4. The CO₂ limit for this model was set to zero, representing the country's net zero target. As part of this model, only renewable generation was extendable, to produce a fully renewable system. Therefore, “extendable_carriers> Generator” was an empty list and “estimate_renewable_capacities> p_nom_max” was recorded as False. Other options in the configuration file are similar to the 2030 scenario.

Figure 3.9 Demand forecasts for 2060 based on demand values from 2030, 2040 and 2050.

3.3.5 Scenario with DAC

As Saudi Arabia plans to utilize carbon capture technologies and continue to use fossil fuels to some extent, models with DAC were considered as an addition to the work of this thesis. DAC was chosen among other technologies due to it being a separate component that could be added to PyPSA-Africa, whereas other CCUS technologies are integrated with components that are mostly part of PyPSA-Earth-SEC. As a result, a script to add DAC to PyPSA-Africa was created, largely using the work in PyPSA-Earth-SEC as inspiration. The script simply defines adding DAC as a link between the network buses and an atmosphere bus, as well as connecting through a link to a CO₂ store. The script was added as part of PyPSA-Africa's script file “add_extra_components”, starting from line 209 within the “attach_stores” function. Appendix C.2 shows the script that was implemented for adding DAC to PyPSA-Africa. DAC was tested for 2060 scenarios with the addition of OCGT and CCGT as extendable carriers (“extendable_carriers> Generator: [OCGT,CCGT]”). This is performed to check if it is optimal to continue consuming fossil fuels, mainly gas, in electricity generation. Other settings are similar to the 2060 main scenario.

3.4 Representation and Validation

The main output of PyPSA-Africa is a netCDF file that contains all the data of the optimized network. PyPSA-Africa has several scripts for plotting and representing different outputs of the network file, as python script files or as Jupiter Notebooks. These outputs include but are not limited to generation mix, spatial distribution of different technologies, system costs, locational LCOE and many others. These scripts, in addition to others that were created, were used to represent different characteristics of the optimized network. The validation of the models from different work packages was performed by comparing what PyPSA-Africa generated to what was found by data collection from public sources. Microsoft Excel was also used to generate some of the graphs presented in this thesis.

3.5 Summary

This chapter discussed the methods that were followed to build and validate the models considered for this thesis. Data collection was a challenging procedure as public data for Saudi Arabia are limited. However, some data were found and compared to the data and models that were built by PyPSA-Africa's work packages. As for modelling, options in the configuration file in PyPSA-Africa have been modified for different scenarios. Main modifications are the electricity load value for the specific year, the CO2 limit, and the choice of different extendable carriers. A model with DAC was taken into account by creating a new script to add DAC as part of "add_extra_components" script file. Excel and Jupiter Notebooks were mainly used for representation of results along with other default scripts of PyPSA-Africa. Moreover, validation was performed by comparing the outputs of PyPSA-Africa to the collected data.

Chapter 4: Results

This chapter discusses the results of the models built for this thesis. The outputs of PyPSA-Africa include those from the work packages such as demand modelling, cleaned data for existing power plants and networks, renewable energy profiles of the country, and land constraints as well as the final netCDF network file. Validation of the outputs from PyPSA-Africa's work packages is performed in comparison with public sources. The characteristics of the output network models such as the generation mix, network infrastructure, storage, hourly dispatch, curtailment and costs are presented. Due to the uncertainty in forecasting the demand for 2060, a sensitivity analysis was performed to test different demand forecasts and their effect on system characteristics.

The structure of this chapter is as follows: Validation of work packages models is presented in Section 4.1. The characteristics of the network models are explored in Section 4.2. The sensitivity analysis of different demand forecasts is discussed in Section 4.3. The chapter concludes with a short summary.

4.1 Validation

It is crucial to validate PyPSA-Africa results for Saudi Arabia in order to assess the network models' accuracy and highlight areas for development. Unfortunately, Saudi Arabia is still lagging in terms of making its electricity system's open data available. Nevertheless, PyPSA-Africa outputs are compared to the data gathered for the nation's system, as part of Section 3.2. Due to a lack of numerical data, visual validation of maps or graphs is frequently used throughout the thesis.

4.1.1 Demand

Validation of time series as well as total demand generated by PyPSA-Africa through GEGIS is performed to check the reliability of demand forecasting of PyPSA-Africa. When reflecting the total demand forecasted by PyPSA-Africa into the actual demand data collected from OurWorldInData (OWID)¹⁰, it does not follow a linear or exponential trend, due to the many factors that can affect demand forecasting. Nonetheless, the demand increment in each decade appears to be of reasonable value, as illustrated in **Figure 4.1**. Accordingly, the time series demand curves generated in Section 3.2.2 are compared to the one generated by PyPSA-Africa for the base network, as shown in **Figure 4.2**. The annual distribution of the demand follows the same trend with a very high load in the summer compared to the winter, due to high temperatures and the use of air conditioning. However, the total demand from PyPSA-Africa is lower than the other estimated demand. Moreover, the daily variation of the time series demand seems lower in PyPSA-Africa than with other estimations.

Figure 4.1 Saudi Arabia's demand forecast by PyPSA-Africa in comparison with actual demand from OWID.

Figure 4.2 Time series demand obtained from PyPSA-Africa compared to the one generated in Section 3.2.2.

4.1.2 Power plants and network topology

The total number of existing power plants considered by PyPSA-Africa is 67, with a total capacity of around 81,500 MW, approximately 9 GW less than the capacity reported by WERA [88]. This discrepancy is a result of an issue encountered with PyPSA-Africa that was recently resolved but not implemented in the models because of time limitation. Additionally, the number of power plants is considerably different, most likely as a result of confusion over the difference between power plants and power plant units. Transmission lines modelled by PyPSA-Africa are shown in **Figure 4.3**, along with

Figure 4.3 Transmission lines and population distribution of Saudi Arabia, generated by PyPSA-Africa.

population distribution. This illustration appears to be an updated version of the one shown in **Figure 3.7**. The total length of the lines generated by PyPSA-Africa is around 39.5 thousand kilometers. PyPSA-Africa takes 220, 300 and 380 kV lines as input, while the actual lines are 230 and 380 kV, according to WERA's report [88]. This could be the reason for the difference in the lengths of transmission lines, shown in **Table 4.1**.

Table 4.1 Comparison between the power plants and lines data between PyPSA-Africa and WERA's report.

	Unit	PyPSA-Africa	WERA's report
Number of power plants	#	67	84
Total capacity of power plants	GW	90	81.5
Length of 220,230 kV lines	Thousand km	18.4	4.2
Length of 380 kV lines	Thousand km	21.1	39.4

4.1.3 Land constraints and available RES

The land cover constraints as well as the distribution of wind speed and solar irradiance over the country are generated by PyPSA-Africa in order to develop renewable energy profiles used as an input to the model. The land cover constraints in Saudi Arabia are mainly natural reserves and protected areas as covered in Section 3.2.3. However, PyPSA-Africa, as shown in **Figure 4.4**, only considered the constraints of the highest density urban areas and regions with challenging terrain in the southeast when assessing available areas for renewable installations. This is due to a limitation in the GIS data for

protected areas, which is only relevant to the African continent, although there is ongoing work to resolve this issue²⁶.

Figure 4.4 Available areas for RES installation estimated by PyPSA-Africa.

The spatial distribution of average DNI and wind speeds is also generated by PyPSA-Africa through collected data, as presented in **Figure 4.5**. These distributions are similar to the ones found in the literature, shown in **Figures 2.7** and **2.10**. The resulting renewable profiles for onshore wind and solar energy are illustrated in **Figure 4.6**. Both profiles show considerable potential, with higher solar energy potential, whereas wind energy is limited by land constraints.

Figure 4.5 Spatial distribution of average DNI and wind speeds.

Figure 4.6 Solar and wind renewable profiles estimated by PyPSA-Africa.

²⁶<https://github.com/pypsa-meets-africa/pypsa-africa/issues/411>

4.2 Network Models

All of the data from the forecasted networks by PyPSA-Africa are saved in the netCDF file, with many components representing different characteristics of the network²⁷ including the generation mix, lines and network infrastructure, storage units, hourly dispatch, curtailment, costs, and many others. The output models represent the scenarios discussed in Section 3.3. The first being the base scenario which was used mostly for validation, therefore will not be of interest further. Second is the 2030 scenario as a transitioning phase with half the emissions. Finally, two 2060 models representing the net zero target, a fully renewable (FR) model, and one with DAC technology. Different features of these models are discussed, with more focus on the estimated generation mix. An overview of the key characteristics of the energy systems produced by the models in this study can be found in **Table 4.2**.

Table 4.2 General characteristics of the models' energy systems.

	Unit	2030	2060 FR	2060 DAC
Generation Capacity	GW	86.37	700.72	527.99
Storage Capacity	GW	8.97	262.99	186.34
Line Expansion	GW	33.34	62.38	25.33
System cost	Billion SAR / yr	112.27	275.97	237.21
Average marginal price	SAR/kWh	0.186	0.272	0.185

4.2.1 Total and spatial generation mix

The generation mix represents the percentages of different electricity generation technologies for each model. **Figure 4.7** shows the total and spatial generation mix for the different models. This starts from the base model, where fossil fuels are dominant in electricity generation. Oil is the major contributor with 60% of the generation mix, whereas gas represents almost all of the remaining generation. Renewables in the base network are very small in comparison and almost negligible. The base network employs a significant quantity of fossil fuels to generate electricity, thus the generation capacity appears to be concentrated around areas with higher load and fuel accessibility. Consequently, it has been noticed that the highest generation is located in the eastern region, most likely due to the availability of oil and gas reserves. In addition, significant cities such as Makkah in the west and Riyadh in the centre have a greater generation than the rest of the country, next only to the eastern region. Moreover, the use of gas in electricity generation for the base network is higher by CCGT than the less efficient OCGT, as represented in **Figure 2.12**. Furthermore, gas generation is generally in the eastern region, with a small

²⁷<https://pypsa.readthedocs.io/en/latest/components.html#>

amount in the central region. The western region only utilizes oil for generation. Additionally, there is limited electricity generation in the southern and northern regions.

The model constructed for 2030 with half of the current emissions shows interesting results. More penetration of renewable energy is seen due to the limitation of CO₂ emissions, representing around 50% of the generation. Remarkably, onshore wind energy appears relatively advantageous compared to solar energy and has potential across the nation. However, solar energy still makes up 25% of generation, with more installations occurring in the southwest, northwest, and locations close to the centre, which have higher irradiance. Due to the use of renewables, electricity generation is distributed around the country. This has many benefits and will reduce the need for an expensive transmission network infrastructure. Additionally, it will reduce transmission line losses by generation being close to loads. The generation mix also includes CCGT and OCGT, with CCGT dominating due to its lower emissions. Nevertheless, their use is restricted to locations with a higher demand.

Figure 4.7 Total and spatial generation mix of different models.

The fully renewable model for the 2060 net zero target has a very high penetration of solar energy, accounting for 98% of its generation. The solar installations are widely spread across the country with different capacities based on demand distribution and available network. Onshore wind energy represents the remaining 2% of the generation, with installations in the northern region and east coast, both with a considerable potential for wind energy applications. Contrary to the 2030 model, this model appears to depend on solar energy more than wind.

Finally, the model for net zero 2060 with DAC technology provides unique results. Solar energy is still dominating the energy mix, with a percentage of 82%, which is lower than the model with a fully renewable installation. The distribution of solar energy appears to be similar to the previous model. Nonetheless, the remaining generation is composed of wind energy, CCGT, and OCGT, with percentages of 4, 7 and 6%, respectively. Wind energy is utilized in the north and east coast, similar to the FR model as well as an area in the southwest. In comparison to the FR model, the percentage of wind energy in the generation mix with DAC is higher. Since DAC captures emissions from the atmosphere, it is considered as a negative emissions technology, which allows for some installation of CCGT and OCGT, with positive emissions, resulting in net zero emissions. CCGT is also higher than OCGT in the mix of this model. Gas generation is located in similar buses to the model built for 2030. Furthermore, it has been observed that the solar energy capacity in most areas is rather large, in the FR model, in order to meet the peak summer load, whereas it is reduced in the DAC model due to the use of CCGT and OCGT to match the peak demand.

4.2.2 Network infrastructure

The option of 30 clusters for the models leads PyPSA-Africa to aggregate the different transmission lines and power plants to the required resolution. Therefore, the resulting transmission network is an overview of the aggregated lines. **Figure 4.8** illustrates the aggregated existing lines and the expected lines' expansion for different models. The estimated expansion is mostly affected by the capacity of generation from different buses. The 2030 model has a relatively low expansion, mainly in the central and southwest areas. As for the 2060 FR model, Central areas appear to have the greatest expansion due to higher distributed generation. With DAC technology, expansion is related to areas that require electricity from CCGT or OCGT technologies.

Figure 4.8 Aggregated existing and expanded transmission lines.

4.2.3 Storage

The models take into account energy storage in the form of batteries and hydrogen storage. All of the models indicated that hydrogen storage was extremely limited, whereas battery storage was highly advantageous. For the 2030 model, the total storage is limited due to the use of both wind and solar energy, as well as the high percentages of CCGT and OCGT. However, this limited storage is still required to cover for some of the peak load in the summer, as shown through the battery state of charge in **Figure 4.9**. The 2060 fully renewable model has a substantial amount of battery storage due solely to its dependence on intermittent renewables. This reliance on batteries is largely reduced when implementing DAC into the model, owing to the operation of CCGT and OCGT which help meet the peak load. In both 2060 models, there is a noticeable fluctuation of the batteries state of charge in the summer, most likely due to the peak load, whereas it is almost constant for the rest of the year, as shown in **Figure 4.9**. The fluctuations in the 2060 FR model appear more frequent in comparison to the 2060 with DAC model as the presence of gas technologies in the DAC model lowers the dependency on battery storage. The spatial distribution of the storage capacities follows that of higher solar generation, as shown in **Figure 4.10**.

Figure 4.9 Storage state of charge for the various models.

Figure 4.10 Spatial distribution of battery storage.

4.2.4 Hourly dispatch and curtailment

The hourly electricity dispatch is an indicator of how different generation technologies operate throughout the year. The total generation in each instant should match the demand in order to maintain a stable system. As the electricity peak demand for Saudi Arabia is in the summer, the generation reaches its maximum capacity. **Figure 4.11** illustrates the hourly dispatch for the multiple models in a ten-day period in both the winter and summer. For the 2030 scenario, conventional generation accounts for about 50% of the summer demand due to the peak load. It can be seen that CCGT significantly contributes to generation when it is used in both the winter and summer. On the contrary, OCGT is mostly utilized throughout the summer. In terms of renewable energy, solar power seems to be the main source during the day, while wind power is used at night. Evidently, storage use is severely constrained because of the high gas generation during peak load. The 2060 FR model is dominated by solar generation with battery storage. A small amount of wind energy is utilized in the summer. The generation from solar is relatively high in order to account for the load as well as the charge required for the battery so that it can be discharged to meet the demand at nighttime. This trend is followed in both the winter and summer. Additionally, the summer peak load necessitated the erection of very large solar energy installations that are not required in the winter. By utilizing more CCGT and OCGT, the 2060 DAC model performs better in terms of the solar capacity needed at peak load, lowering the capacity required for battery storage. Moreover, this model follows a similar dispatch to the 2060 FR model and is virtually entirely renewable in the winter. Both in the winter and summer, there is a slight penetration of wind energy. However, hydrogen dispatch is minuscule and nearly nonexistent in all models. Furthermore, it appears that the load is relatively higher throughout daytime, likely as a result of the higher temperature.

Figure 4.11 Average hourly dispatch of the models.

In general, curtailment is necessary for most renewable energy projects due to capturing more energy when demand is lower. However, higher values are an indicator of inadequate system sizing. As seen in **Figure 4.12**, all the models exhibit larger curtailment during the winter, in the off-peak load period. Additionally, the curtailment of renewable energy increases with capacity. This can be observed in the 2030 model, when wind energy is curtailed to a considerably greater extent than solar energy. Moreover, solar curtailment is significantly larger than wind curtailment in both models for 2060. The DAC model exhibits less curtailment than the FR model since it makes use of conventional generation particularly in the summer when CCGT and OCGT are heavily employed. In all models, wind energy is mostly reduced during the daytime when solar power predominates.

Figure 4.12 Solar and curtailments for all models.

4.2.5 Costs

The system costs and marginal prices for all models as a consequence of PyPSA-Africa's implementation of a least cost optimization built in PyPSA are the lowest that could be achieved. The average marginal price as well as the overall annual system cost for each model are displayed in **Table 4.2**. The system cost is lower in 2030 than it is in 2060 because there are likely to be fewer new renewable energy installations in 2030. Due to the heavy consumption of battery storage, the FR model appears to have the highest system cost. For the FR model, the average marginal price is likewise the highest. The average marginal prices for the DAC models for 2030 and 2060, however, are comparable in value. As seen in **Figure 4.13**, the average temporal marginal price also varies by location, with higher generating locations being more expensive.

Figure 4.13 Locational marginal price maps for all models.

4.3 Sensitivity Analysis

Due to the simple methodology employed in this thesis for demand forecasting, a sensitivity analysis was performed to examine the consequences of modifying the demand on different system features. The analysis was carried out through the 2060 models with $\pm 15\%$ of the demand forecasted for the 2060 FR model. The results of the analysis are summarized in **Figure 4.14**. Wind and solar generation appear to follow a close percentage with the load, as well as the curtailment of solar energy. The curtailment of wind energy was lowered in both scenarios with increasing and decreasing of the load. Additionally, lowering the load produced low hydrogen storage, but raising it produced a lower value. Whereas, battery storage slightly increased when the load was increased, but then declined comparatively when the load was reduced. The expansion of the lines seems to be in accordance with the pattern of the varying load at greater percentages. On the contrary, while the average marginal price is almost constant across all scenarios, the system cost fluctuates roughly in line with the load.

Figure 4.14 The effects of varying the load on different system characteristics.

4.4 Summary

The validation of the PyPSA-Africa work packages' models, which served as an input for network optimization, was covered in this chapter. These models take into account the potential for installing RES as well as demand, power plants, the transmission network, and land constraints. This chapter presents the outcomes of modelling the network of various scenarios. This study concentrated on three primary scenarios: a 2030 scenario, a 2060 scenario with DAC technology, and a 2060 scenario with 100% renewable energy. Based on several system characteristics, including the generation mix, network infrastructure, storage capacity, curtailment, hourly dispatch, and costs, the models that emerged from these scenarios were assessed. The 2030 model uses 50% renewable energy, has greater wind energy, and has limited storage capacity; hence it is less expensive. Solar energy dominates the 2060 fully renewable model, which increased the requirement for battery storage, thereby raising the price. The 2060 DAC model, in contrast, uses a modest fraction of CCGT and OCGT, which has a considerable impact on reducing the need for batteries and, consequently, prices. Finally, a sensitivity analysis was performed to determine the impact of changing the system's input load.

Chapter 5: Discussion

In this chapter, the findings of the thesis are analyzed and discussed critically. The validation process was addressed on how the inputs to PyPSA-Africa, which represent Saudi Arabia's current system, compare to the actual data that were publicly available. Moreover, the results of the output models built by PyPSA-Africa are analyzed based on systems' characteristics. As PyPSA-Africa is currently limited to power network modelling, general evaluation of the energy system is derived from the model outputs and findings in the literature. The limitations surrounding this thesis are also addressed. Finally, conclusions of this work are drawn with suggestions for future work,

Therefore, this chapter's structure is as follows: The analysis of the input and output models used in PyPSA-Africa is presented in Section 5.1. The recommendations for the energy system are covered in Section 5.2. In Section 5.3, the thesis' limitations are discussed. In Section 5.4, final conclusions are demonstrated. Section 5.5 offers suggestions for additional research and work.

5.1 Analysis of the Power Networks

Analysis of the power networks generated by PyPSA-Africa is performed covering two aspects: first is the input models that are the results of the work packages integrated in PyPSA-Africa, second is the output network models generated by PyPSA-Africa after setting up the scenarios' configuration and data assumptions.

5.1.1 Input models and data

Acquiring data for Saudi Arabia was challenging since a large quantity of it has been lost. Nevertheless, the data presented in this work were collected from official sources such as WERA and SEC reports, from the available literature, and through PyPSA-Africa from open datahubs. Moreover, Saudi Arabia is moving towards open data sharing by establishing its first open data website²⁸. However, this effort is still in an early phase, and the shared data are mostly outdated. Consequently, governing this and providing recent, more reliable data is recommended in order to promote research related to the country.

The weekly demand data acquired from WERA and reflected to the hourly demand of Egypt and Arizona present similar results. However, the forecasted demand generated by GEGIS on PyPSA-Africa follows a similar pattern with lower daily variations. Both methods present a reliable result when it comes to the annual demand. However, they show less accurate results when considering the daily variations of

²⁸<https://data.gov.sa/en/home>

demand. Demand forecasting for Saudi Arabia in the literature is limited to 2030 [85] [92], with a number of predictions based on growth against consumption efficiency policies. The forecasted demand for 2030 by GEGIS appear to agree with the forecast of [85] with a 5.1% average annual growth rate (AAGR). Nevertheless, forecasting demand for a long-term period such as up to 2060 has great uncertainties and requires extensive research which is out of the scope of this thesis. Therefore, the simplified method used in this study, which involved forecasting the demand through linear regression from the values predicted by GEGIS for previous years and then performing sensitivity analysis on the outputs when the demand was changed by 15%, seems to be an appropriate approach. On the contrary, it is apparent that GEGIS's locational forecasting of demand could use some refinement; this may be due to load aggregation limitation, addressed in [13]. Finally, there are ongoing discussions to develop a separate GitHub repository for demand forecasting for any prediction year and incorporate it with PyPSA-Africa.

The majority of the country's protected areas were not taken into consideration by the land constraints generated by Atlite through PyPSA-Africa; this is most likely due to the ongoing issue with the GIS data of nations other than those in Africa. It is thought that PyPSA-Africa could manually include these regions. In contrast, Saudi Arabia has extensive uninhabited lands that might be used for renewable installation sites; thus, area is generally not a problem. Moreover, the country plans to plant trees as part of SGI throughout the majority of its areas in order to reduce emissions, which could limit the use of renewable energy. Furthermore, there is no clear policy on the installation of renewable energy projects.

The renewables considered for this study are solar PV, onshore and offshore wind energy, since other renewables have very low potential in Saudi Arabia, except for CSP, which is being incorporated into PyPSA-Africa²⁹. The potential of offshore wind energy was nonexistent, most likely due to the relatively narrow seas, west and east of the country. The land constraint assumption by PyPSA-Africa has led to renewable energy profiles that show potential in almost all of the country. This is based on selected technologies, CSI PV and Vista V112 for solar and wind, respectively. However, it is a contradiction when considering available literature where the northwest showed the highest potential of solar and wind energy exploitation, with a considerable potential of solar in the southwest. Nonetheless, it appears that these technologies will operate across the country according to the estimated renewable profiles generated by PyPSA-Africa, which is beneficial since it will result in distributed generation that lowers the need for an extensive network infrastructure.

The data collected and cleaned by PyPSA-Africa for the existing power plants and their capacities look similar to that of WERA. However, the data for the lines look quite different, especially the difference in the length of the lines in accordance with their nominal voltage. This is an addressed issue to

²⁹<https://github.com/pypsa-meets-africa/pypsa-africa/issues/145>

the models of this study which needs to be resolved by cleaning the data manually, and will require more time than allocated for this thesis. Nevertheless, the general results of the models should not be largely affected by this issue, although resolving it would lead to more accurate results.

The hourly temporal resolution considered in this study produces fair and reasonable results. However, it is believed that the spatial resolution could be improved by increasing the number of clusters to gain more accurate results, as stated in [114]. Nonetheless, the 30 clusters resolution was considered in order to lower computation time. Moreover, the aggregation of lines and power plants into the required cluster might not reflect the actual infrastructure of the network. Therefore, default assumptions were followed and approximated.

The PyPSA-Africa assumptions are the source of the cost assumptions employed in this thesis. While the assumptions for the 2060 models were anticipated using Excel functions employing assumptions from earlier years, those for the 2030 model were obtained directly. Due to the dearth of assumptions for 2060 and the significant research required to estimate costs for 2060, this approach was followed. This method produced reasonable findings, but there is still some uncertainty surrounding it, necessitating further research. It is also worth mentioning that the cost assumptions in PyPSA-Africa are global, and the local costs for each technology is difficult to obtain, although they might be lower in the KSA for certain technologies, especially conventional ones. Nonetheless, Saudi Arabia is gradually lifting the subsidies on power and water, which could lead to following international energy prices.

5.1.2 Output models

The models considered for this study are a base model, mainly for validation, a model for 2030 as a transition phase and to compare to the country's Vision 2030 goals, and several models to reflect the net zero target of the country in 2060. The models of 2060 include fully renewable models with varying load to perform the sensitivity analysis, and finally a model with DAC technology to estimate the system if the KSA is considering continuing the use of fossil fuels. These scenarios were developed to cover as many assumptions for the power system of 2060 as possible. However, there are other factors that could alter the results of these models, mainly the huge economic transition that the country is going through, with the construction of city-scale projects. Most of these factors are still in the vision phase, and lack clear data. Therefore, they were not included as part of this study.

The base model built for this study shows a generation mix that is dominated by oil. However, the current generation mix is dominated by gas, which shows that the power plants' data collected by PyPSA-Africa are outdated. Nevertheless, the existing power plants were not considered when building the other models, as it is planned to phase out oil due to its low efficiency and high emissions, thus changing the

whole generation mix. On the other hand, the spatial distribution of the existing power plants appears to be rather accurate. In the current network, penetration of renewables and storage is generally minimal.

The model built for 2030 shows interesting results when compared to the aims of Vision 2030. The penetration of renewables has a similar percentage of 50%, where wind energy has the largest percentage. This is probably due to wind energy being dominant at nighttime when solar is diminished and having a lower cost than storage units. Furthermore, the other half of the mix is dominated by CCGT which has more efficiency than OCGT and oil. The conventional generators play a major role in eliminating the need for battery storage, especially at peak load. The goals of Vision 2030 incorporate solar energy more than wind, which might lead to a higher cost of batteries or more reliance on conventional generation at nighttime, leading to more emissions.

The net zero fully renewable 2060 model resulted in a significantly high penetration of solar energy, along with battery storage. Wind energy represented only 2% of the generation. This is due to the assumed investment cost of battery storage dropping with time, making it more feasible than wind energy when used at night. Moreover, the general potential of solar energy appears to be higher across the whole country. However, this installation has led to a large amount of curtailment at off-peak load. The sensitivity analysis performed by varying the load of this model resulted in similar variations for most of the system characteristics. Nevertheless, the general generation mix remained the same.

The net zero model for 2060 with integrating DAC technology was developed to examine the system with a carbon capture technology. DAC was considered in this study due to the simplicity of adding it as a separate component to PyPSA-Africa, compared to other CCUS technologies. Although DAC is one of the most expensive carbon capture technologies³⁰, the results of its model were more feasible than the fully renewable system. This is largely due to allowing the operation of CCGT and OCGT, while capturing their emissions at peak load, which decreases the capacity needed for both solar energy and battery storage. However, the penetration of solar energy and battery storage is still considerably high in this model. Wind energy, conversely, did not seem appealing and was limited to 4%, most likely due to the technology almost reaching its optimal design for onshore installations, and because the reduction of its investment cost is less than that of solar and battery storage. Even though CCGT and OCGT are utilized in this system, there is still a large amount of curtailment, especially with solar energy, due to its capacity exceeding consumption in the winter. The attempt to incorporate DAC into PyPSA-Africa is inspired by the work on PyPSA-Earth-Sec. However, it only considers the electricity part of DAC, while ignoring the heat part, which is implemented in PyPSA-Earth-Sec. Nevertheless, its application in PyPSA-Africa is relatively valid in terms of reducing emissions.

³⁰<https://www.iea.org/reports/direct-air-capture>

The estimated expansion of the network in all models did not seem particularly accurate. The generation capacity, especially for the 2060 models, far exceeds that of the original network. Therefore, the expected network infrastructure should be much larger than what was found in these models. This could have happened due to one of two reasons. First is that the distributed generation of renewables is well optimized so that line expansions are minimum. Second is due to the issue of line aggregation not representing the actual network and showing some lines with larger capacities than they actually are.

In terms of costs, the fully renewable model had the highest system cost because of the large use of batteries, whereas the 2060 with DAC model had a system cost that is almost double of the 2030 model. This pattern could be an indication of a well-structured system. Moreover, the average marginal price for the fully renewable 2060 model is the highest, whereas it is of similar value for both 2030 and 2060 with DAC models. Additionally, this value is not far from the current low tariff of 0.18 SAR/kWh. Moreover, this low marginal price is beneficial in developing policies for power pricing according to [115], which could ensure energy security and sustain the use of renewables at an affordable price. It is worth mentioning that PyPSA-Africa optimizes on the least-cost basis, without taking into account any market scheme, and the resulting price is lower than any competitive market that could be implemented.

As PyPSA-Africa is transitioning towards PyPSA-Earth and PyPSA-Earth-Sec, there is huge ongoing development to resolve the current issues and introduce new features and technologies to the tool. Despite the current limitations and issues, its results are still reliable, and policies could be derived from it. A major advantage in using PyPSA-Africa is its flexibility of adding other components to the system and manipulation of data to suit many different scenarios for numerous countries. There is also ongoing work to incorporate different electricity market schemes in PyPSA-Africa and analyze their effects. As a consequence, this could be very beneficial to Saudi Arabia in the future as its market is still immature.

5.2 Analysis of the Energy System

Energy transition plans are trending across the globe, and each country is racing to acquire the lead in new technologies for generating, storing, and transmitting energy. Saudi Arabia, as announced in its Vision 2030 and SGI, is planning to have a major role in generating solar energy, producing hydrogen and capturing carbon. These plans are in compliance with the Paris agreement. The results of this study indicate that this is the optimal approach for Saudi Arabia, along with incorporating more battery storage with solar energy. However, in the short-term goals for 2030, wind energy seems more feasible than solar. On the contrary, CSP technology shows promising potential in Saudi Arabia, especially when integrating it with other technologies such as CCGT or water desalination. CSP is mostly beneficial in very high temperatures, which would increase in the worst-case scenarios of climate change, leading to a drop in the efficiency of PV. In addition, the findings of this thesis justify the high interest in solar energy observed

in the literature. Other renewables such as hydro, ocean and geothermal energy show insignificant potential in the country, although biomass, in terms of energy from waste, indicates a promising future. Nuclear energy, conversely, does not seem to be a cost-effective option; rather, it is more of a political decision the nation is considering. Fossil fuels could be the economic driver of the country's energy transition, as phasing out oil from the generation mix will allow for higher revenue from oil exports. However, the country still needs to compensate for its consumption-based CO₂ emissions, mostly using DAC. Furthermore, the extraction of gas does not appear as great as that of oil, and the use of it in electricity generation is advantageous, as shown in the 2030 and 2060 with DAC models. Therefore, using it locally appears more feasible than exporting it, in the case that its production does not increase by discovering new reserves in the future. Moreover, coal is mostly used in industry and has very little other usage in the nation.

Operation of the power system could contribute to the whole energy system. For example, introducing demand side management policies to control demand in the summer could reduce the required capacity and improve the whole system's performance. In addition, distributed generation through renewables will limit the need for significant expansion of the network. Moreover, the use of carbon capture technologies appears to be the optimal choice when the capacity of renewables is extensive and there is large curtailment. Furthermore, battery storage is essential when considering high penetration of solar energy of the KSA. As shown in the results for 2060, there is a large curtailment in the winter caused by the high capacity of solar energy. This curtailment can be avoided, and energy can be economically utilized by exporting it directly through interconnections, or converting it into hydrogen for trade purposes. In addition, introducing new developed market schemes to the electricity sector in Saudi Arabia would increase the competitiveness and affordability of power in comparison with the current SEC's monopoly.

5.3 Limitations

The major limitation for this thesis is time. Evaluation and planning of an energy system for an entire country requires sophisticated research that will take more time than that assigned to this thesis. For example, many runs of the PyPSA-Africa package have been performed in order to test it and resolve some of the errors that were encountered. Moreover, the continuous development of the PyPSA-Africa package required continuous updates and occasional rerunning. In addition, some of the parameters were adjusted such as spatiotemporal resolutions to decrease computation time. Additionally, there were major updates to PyPSA-Africa in its comigration and scripts recently, which limited time prevented further implementation in this thesis. Accordingly, this study could be expanded further with higher resolution in the future.

Chapter 6: Conclusions and Future Work

6.1 Conclusions

This is a first attempt to predict the energy system for Saudi Arabia in 2060, with net zero emissions. Energy transition plans are becoming more essential as the effects of climate change are soaring. Saudi Arabia is taking serious steps towards lowering its emissions and being more environmentally friendly. PyPSA, through the PyPSA-Africa package, was employed to build models for the energy system. The models in this study include a base model for validation, a model for 2030, to compare to the country's Vision 2030 and as a transition phase, and two models for 2060 net zero, one is fully renewable and the other has DAC technology. The models were evaluated, and recommendations have been drawn for the 2060 energy system, based on the generation mix, storage, network expansion, hourly dispatch, curtailment and costs.

When PyPSA-Africa's collected and cleaned data was validated, it produced relatively accurate predictions of the potential for renewable energy sources and the demand for electricity. However, an update to the data is necessary for the transmission network and power plants that are currently in operation. Furthermore, PyPSA-Africa's estimate of the protected areas in the KSA is lower than the actual natural reserves, hence, it is advised that the work package is expanded. Saudi Arabia's electricity network has few publicly accessible data; thus, the nation is urged to share more information in order to advance system research.

The results of the models built in this study indicate that when the battery storage cost is higher than wind energy in 2030, wind energy penetration increases to account for the load at nighttime. However, in 2060, solar energy is dominant with battery storage, assuming the batteries' cost drops rapidly. Furthermore, adoption of carbon capture technologies such as DAC resulted in a lower generation capacity and appears to be more feasible than having a fully renewable system. The resulting average marginal cost of the 2060 model with DAC is around 0.185 SAR/kWh, which is considerably low and almost matches the current electricity tariff of 0.18 SAR/kWh.

The peak load in the summer and its day and night variations poses the most challenging time of the energy system in Saudi Arabia, due to higher temperatures. Therefore, increasing the efficiency of energy consumption at that time is recommended as well as adopting demand side management techniques. Moreover, the system capacity optimized for that load results in a large curtailment of renewables. Nevertheless, this curtailment could be reduced by exporting electricity through interconnections or producing hydrogen.

The renewables considered in the models of this thesis are solar PV, onshore and offshore wind energy. However, other renewables still show potential in the future such as CSP and waste energy.

Nuclear energy, on the other hand, was not found to be cost effective, although more interest has been drawn towards it due to political reasons. Finally, the work in this thesis is an initial proposal of the energy system of Saudi Arabia in 2060 and could be used as a guidance to policymakers in the country.

6.2 Future Work

There is a large gap when it comes to the research of energy systems in Saudi Arabia, as many studies are limited. This is an opportunity for researchers of the country and out with to further study the systems. Additionally, official public data regarding details of the system are lacking, and non-official data is highly unreliable.

Accordingly, the work in this thesis can be further expanded and improved through acquiring more accurate data about the energy system in Saudi Arabia: by contacting public and private entities in the country. Moreover, the method used for demand forecasting is a simplified approach and a more sophisticated method could lead to more reliable results. Furthermore, increasing the spatiotemporal resolution is advised as it will generate more accurate findings. In addition, including other renewable technologies such as CSP will support the development of PyPSA-Africa/Earth and may lead to more feasible systems. Applying the PyPSA-Earth-Sec package to Saudi Arabia, once it is fully developed to use in several countries, can be seen as an extension to this study, where more sectors, other CCUS technologies and different energy carriers can be implemented. Finally, the author hopes to contribute further to the PyPSA-Africa/Earth projects.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Energy Modelling Software

A.1. Types of various energy modelling software analysed by [10].

Tool	Type						
	Simulation	Scenario	Equilibrium	Top-down	Bottom-up	Operation optimisation	Investment optimisation
AEOLIUS	✓				✓		
BALMOREL	✓	✓	Partial		✓	✓	✓
BCHP Screening Tool	✓				✓	✓	
COMPOSE					✓	✓	✓
E4cast		✓	✓		✓		✓
EMCAS	✓	✓			✓		✓
EMINENT		✓			✓		
EMPS						✓	
EnergyPLAN	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
energyPRO	✓	✓				✓	✓
ENPEP-BALANCE		✓	✓	✓			
GTMax	✓					✓	
H2RES	✓	✓			✓	✓	
HOMER	✓				✓	✓	✓
HYDROGEMS		✓					
IKARUS		✓			✓		✓
INFORSE		✓					
Invert	✓	✓			✓		✓
LEAP	✓	✓		✓	✓		
MARKAL/TIMES		✓	✓	Partial	✓		✓
Mesap PlaNet		✓			✓		
MESSAGE		✓	Partial		✓	✓	✓
MiniCAM	✓	✓	Partial	✓	✓		
NEMS		✓	✓				
ORCED	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓
PERSEUS		✓	✓		✓		✓
PRIMES			✓				
ProdRisk	✓					✓	✓
RAMSES	✓				✓	✓	
RETScreen		✓			✓		✓
SimREN							
SIVAEL							

STREAM	✓					
TRNSYS16	✓	✓			✓	✓
UniSyD3.0		✓	✓		✓	
WASP	✓					✓
WILMAR Planning Tool	✓				✓	

A.2 Comparison of some features of PyPSA and other software [11].

Power system tools	Grid Analysis							Economic Analysis					
	Software	Free Software	Power Flow	Continuation Power Flow	Dynamic Analysis	Transport Model	Linear OPF	SCLOPF	Nonlinear OPF	Multi-Period Optimisation	Unit Commitment	Investment Optimisation	Other Energy Sectors
	MATPOWER	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓				
	NEPLAN		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				✓
	pandapower	✓	✓			✓	✓		✓				
	PowerFactory		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓				
	PowerWorld		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓				
	PSAT	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓		
	PSS/E		✓		✓		✓	✓	✓				
	PSS/SINCAL		✓		✓				✓				✓
	PYPOWER	✓	✓			✓	✓		✓				
	PyPSA	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
Energy system tools	calliope	✓				✓				✓		✓	✓
	minpower	✓					✓	✓			✓	✓	
	MOST	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
	oemof	✓				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓
	OSeMOSYS	✓				✓				✓		✓	✓
	PLEXOS					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
	PowerGAMA	✓				✓	✓			✓			
	PRIMES					✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
	TIMES					✓	✓			✓	✓	✓	✓
	urbs	✓				✓				✓	✓	✓	✓

Appendix B: Default 2030 PyPSA-Africa Costs Assumption and their Projection to 2060.

Technology	Parameter	2030 value	2060 value	Unit
solar-rooftop	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
onwind	lifetime	30	30.83152294	years
offwind	lifetime	30	30.68118406	years
solar	lifetime	25	25.86616973	years
solar-rooftop	lifetime	25	25.86616973	years
solar-utility	lifetime	25	25.86616973	years
PHS	lifetime	80	80	years
hydro	lifetime	80	80	years
ror	lifetime	80	80	years
OCGT	lifetime	30	30	years
nuclear	lifetime	45	45	years
CCGT	lifetime	30	30	years
coal	lifetime	40	40	years
lignite	lifetime	40	40	years
geothermal	lifetime	40	40	years
biomass	lifetime	30	30	years
oil	lifetime	30	30	years
onwind	investment	1040	952.2642743	EUR/kWel
offwind	investment	1640	1342.394255	EUR/kWel
offwind-ac-station	investment	250	250	EUR/kWel
offwind-ac-connection-submarine	investment	2685	2685	EUR/MW/km
offwind-ac-connection-underground	investment	1342	1342	EUR/MW/km
offwind-dc-station	investment	400	400	EUR/kWel
offwind-dc-connection-submarine	investment	2000	2000	EUR/MW/km
offwind-dc-connection-underground	investment	1000	1000	EUR/MW/km
solar	investment	600	404.9165375	EUR/kWel
biomass	investment	2209	2209	EUR/kWel
geothermal	investment	3392	3392	EUR/kWel
coal	investment	1300	1300	EUR/kWel
lignite	investment	1500	1500	EUR/kWel
solar-rooftop	investment	725	484.0440669	EUR/kWel
solar-utility	investment	425	292.432011	EUR/kWel
PHS	investment	2000	2000	EUR/kWel
hydro	investment	2000	2000	EUR/kWel
ror	investment	3000	3000	EUR/kWel
OCGT	investment	400	365.9537141	EUR/kWel
nuclear	investment	6000	6000	EUR/kWel

CCGT	investment	800	747.2760472	EUR/kWel
oil	investment	400	388.8864258	EUR/kWel
onwind	FOM	2.450549	2.3189419	%/year
offwind	FOM	2.304878	2.039146421	%/year
solar	FOM	4.166667	4.77303899	%/year
solar-rooftop	FOM	2	2.492367091	%/year
solar-utility	FOM	3	3.266594365	%/year
biomass	FOM	4.526935	4.526935	%/year
geothermal	FOM	2.358491	2.358491	%/year
coal	FOM	1.923076	1.923076	%/year
lignite	FOM	2	2	%/year
oil	FOM	1.5	1.43896555	%/year
PHS	FOM	1	1	%/year
hydro	FOM	1	1	%/year
ror	FOM	2	2	%/year
CCGT	FOM	2.5	2.403518124	%/year
OCGT	FOM	3.75	3.809360386	%/year
onwind	VOM	2.3	2.055193597	EUR/MWhel
offwind	VOM	2.7	1.876243562	EUR/MWhel
solar	VOM	0.01	0.01	EUR/MWhel
coal	VOM	6	6	EUR/MWhel
lignite	VOM	7	7	EUR/MWhel
CCGT	VOM	4	3.687888161	EUR/MWhel
OCGT	VOM	3	3	EUR/MWhel
nuclear	VOM	8	8	EUR/MWhel
gas	fuel	21.6	21.6	EUR/MWhth
uranium	fuel	3	3	EUR/MWhth
oil	VOM	3	3	EUR/MWhel
nuclear	fuel	3	3	EUR/MWhth
biomass	fuel	7	7	EUR/MWhth
coal	fuel	8.4	8.4	EUR/MWhth
lignite	fuel	2.9	2.9	EUR/MWhth
oil	fuel	50	50	EUR/MWhth
PHS	efficiency	0.75	0.75	per unit
hydro	efficiency	0.9	0.9	per unit
ror	efficiency	0.9	0.9	per unit
OCGT	efficiency	0.39	0.418503737	per unit
CCGT	efficiency	0.5	0.531331121	per unit
biomass	efficiency	0.468	0.468	per unit
geothermal	efficiency	0.239	0.239	per unit
nuclear	efficiency	0.337	0.337	per unit

gas	CO2 intensity	0.187	0.187	tCO2/MWth
coal	efficiency	0.464	0.464	per unit
lignite	efficiency	0.447	0.447	per unit
oil	efficiency	0.393	0.393	per unit
coal	CO2 intensity	0.354	0.354	tCO2/MWth
lignite	CO2 intensity	0.334	0.334	tCO2/MWth
oil	CO2 intensity	0.248	0.248	tCO2/MWth
geothermal	CO2 intensity	0.026	0.026	tCO2/MWth
electrolysis	investment	350	154.8919627	EUR/kWel
electrolysis	FOM	4	398.2936184	%/year
electrolysis	lifetime	18	22.89161455	years
electrolysis	efficiency	0.8	0.916574176	per unit
fuel cell	investment	339	196.0471776	EUR/kWel
fuel cell	FOM	3	3	%/year
fuel cell	lifetime	20	20	years
fuel cell	efficiency	0.58	0.58	per unit
hydrogen storage	investment	11.2	11.2	USD/kWh
hydrogen storage	lifetime	20	20	years
hydrogen underground storage	investment	0.5	0.224568205	EUR/kWh
hydrogen underground storage	lifetime	40	40	years
H2 pipeline	investment	267	267	EUR/MW/km
H2 pipeline	lifetime	40	40	years
H2 pipeline	FOM	5	5	%/year
H2 pipeline	efficiency	0.98	0.98	per unit
methanation	investment	1000	696.2626034	EUR/kWh2
methanation	lifetime	25	25	years
methanation	FOM	3	3	%/year
methanation	efficiency	0.6	0.6	per unit
helmeth	investment	1000	1000	EUR/kW
helmeth	lifetime	25	25	years
helmeth	FOM	3	3	%/year
helmeth	efficiency	0.8	0.8	per unit
DAC	investment	250	121.0446602	EUR/(tCO2/a)
DAC	lifetime	30	30	years
DAC	FOM	4	4	%/year
DAC	electricity-input	0.31	0.253496228	MWh/tCO2
DAC	compression-electricity-input	0.15	0.15	MWh/tCO2
battery inverter	investment	411	50.93133084	USD/kWel
battery inverter	lifetime	20	20	years

battery inverter	efficiency	0.9	0.9021287	per unit charge/discharge
battery inverter	FOM	3	11.65403527	%/year
battery storage	investment	192	75.38182963	USD/kWh
battery storage	lifetime	15	18.02551773	years
decentral air-sourced heat pump	investment	1050	867.8276631	EUR/kWh
decentral air-sourced heat pump	lifetime	20	20	years
decentral air-sourced heat pump	FOM	3.5	3.73302518	%/year
decentral air-sourced heat pump	efficiency	3	3.273097859	per unit
decentral air-sourced heat pump	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
decentral ground-sourced heat pump	investment	1400	1100	EUR/kWh
decentral ground-sourced heat pump	lifetime	20	20	years
decentral ground-sourced heat pump	FOM	3.5	3.927250222	%/year
decentral ground-sourced heat pump	efficiency	4	4.238329121	per unit
decentral ground-sourced heat pump	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
central air-sourced heat pump	investment	700	658.1649379	EUR/kWh
central air-sourced heat pump	lifetime	20	20	years
central air-sourced heat pump	FOM	3.5	3.663700505	%/year
central air-sourced heat pump	efficiency	3	3.1637427	per unit
retrofitting I	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
retrofitting I	lifetime	50	50	years
retrofitting I	FOM	1	1	%/year
retrofitting I	investment	50	50	EUR/m ² /fraction reduction
retrofitting II	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
retrofitting II	lifetime	50	50	years
retrofitting II	FOM	1	1	%/year
retrofitting II	investment	250	250	EUR/m ² /fraction reduction
water tank charger	efficiency	0.9	0.9	per unit
water tank discharger	efficiency	0.9	0.9	per unit
decentral water tank storage	investment	860	860	EUR/m ³
decentral water tank storage	FOM	1	1	%/year
decentral water tank storage	lifetime	20	20	years
decentral water tank storage	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
central water tank storage	investment	30	24.18456714	EUR/m ³
central water tank storage	FOM	1	1.23890518	%/year
central water tank storage	lifetime	40	42.21739451	years
decentral resistive heater	investment	100	100	EUR/kWh
decentral resistive heater	lifetime	20	20	years
decentral resistive heater	FOM	2	2	%/year
decentral resistive heater	efficiency	0.9	0.9	per unit
decentral resistive heater	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
central resistive heater	investment	100	95.3804281	EUR/kWh

central resistive heater	lifetime	20	20	years
central resistive heater	FOM	2	1.788235294	%/year
central resistive heater	efficiency	0.9	0.9	per unit
decentral gas boiler	investment	175	149.782957	EUR/kWhth
decentral gas boiler	lifetime	20	20	years
decentral gas boiler	FOM	2	2.028091336	%/year
decentral gas boiler	efficiency	0.9	0.914136903	per unit
decentral gas boiler	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
central gas boiler	investment	63	59.50760365	EUR/kWhth
central gas boiler	lifetime	22	22	years
central gas boiler	FOM	1	0.897398877	%/year
central gas boiler	efficiency	0.9	0.904654671	per unit
decentral CHP	lifetime	25	25	years
decentral CHP	investment	1400	1400	EUR/kWel
decentral CHP	FOM	3	3	%/year
decentral CHP	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
central CHP	lifetime	25	25	years
central CHP	investment	650	650	EUR/kWel
central CHP	FOM	3	3	%/year
decentral solar thermal	discount rate	0.04	0.04	per unit
decentral solar thermal	FOM	1.3	1.3	%/year
decentral solar thermal	investment	270000	270000	EUR/1000m2
decentral solar thermal	lifetime	20	20	years
central solar thermal	FOM	1.4	1.4	%/year
central solar thermal	investment	140000	140000	EUR/1000m2
central solar thermal	lifetime	20	20	years
HVAC overhead	investment	400	400	EUR/MW/km
HVAC overhead	lifetime	40	40	years
HVAC overhead	FOM	2	2	%/year
HVDC overhead	investment	400	400	EUR/MW/km
HVDC overhead	lifetime	40	40	years
HVDC overhead	FOM	2	2	%/year
HVDC submarine	investment	2000	2000	EUR/MW/km
HVDC submarine	lifetime	40	40	years
HVDC submarine	FOM	2	0.0175	%/year
HVDC inverter pair	investment	150000	150000	EUR/MW
HVDC inverter pair	lifetime	40	40	years
HVDC inverter pair	FOM	2	2	%/year

Appendix C: Main scripts

C.1 Configuration file script

```
# SPDX-FileCopyrightText: : 2021 The PyPSA-Africa Authors
#
# SPDX-License-Identifier: CC0-1.0
version: 0.0.2
tutorial: false

logging:
  level: INFO
  format: "%(levelname)s:%(name)s:%(message)s"

scenario:
  simpl: ['']
  ll: ['copt']
  clusters: [30]
  opts: [Co2L-1H]

countries: ["SA"]

summary_dir: results

snapshots:
  start: "2013-01-01"
  end: "2014-01-01"
  inclusive: "left"

enable:
  retrieve_databundle: false
  download_osm_data: false
  build_natura_raster: false
  build_cutout: false

crs:
  geo_crs: EPSG:4326
  distance_crs: EPSG:3857
  area_crs: ESRI:54009

augmented_line_connection:
  add_to_snakefile: false
  connectivity_upgrade: 3
  new_line_type: "HVDC"
  min_expansion: 1
```

```
cluster_options:
  alternative_clustering: false
  distribute_cluster: ['load']
  out_logging: true

build_shape_options:
  gadm_layer_id: 1
  update_file: false
  out_logging: true
  year: 2020
  nprocesses: 5
  worldpop_method: "standard"
  gdp_method: "standard"

clean_osm_data_options:
  names_by_shapes: true
  threshold_voltage: 35000
  tag_substation: "transmission"
  add_line_endings: true
  generator_name_method: OSM

build_osm_network:
  group_close_buses: true
  group_tolerance_buses: 500
  split_overpassing_lines: true
  overpassing_lines_tolerance: 1

base_network:
  min_voltage_substation_offshore: 35000
  min_voltage_rebase_voltage: 35000

load_options:
  ssp: "ssp2-2.6"
  weather_year: 2013
  prediction_year: 2030 # 2050 for 2060 model
  scale: 1 # 1.25 for 2060 model, 1.1 and 1.4 for varying load models

electricity:
  voltages: [220., 300., 380.]
  co2limit: 0 # Net zero, 2.7105e8 for 2030 half emissions
  co2base: 5.421e8 # Current emissions
  agg_p_nom_limits: data/agg_p_nom_minmax.csv

operational_reserve:
  activate: false
```

```
epsilon_load: 0.02
epsilon_vres: 0.02
contingency: 0

extendable_carriers:
  Generator: [] # [OCGT, CCGT] for DAC and 2030 scenarios
  StorageUnit: [battery, H2]
  Store: [battery, H2]
  Link: []

conventional_carriers: []

max_hours:
  battery: 6
  H2: 168

powerplants_filter:

estimate_renewable_capacities:
  stats: "irena"
  year: 2020
  p_nom_min: 1
  p_nom_max: False # RES expansion
  technology_mapping:
    Offshore: [offwind-ac, offwind-dc]
    Onshore: [onwind]
    PV: [solar]

lines:
  types:
    220.: "Al/St 240/40 2-bundle 220.0"
    300.: "Al/St 240/40 3-bundle 300.0"
    380.: "Al/St 240/40 4-bundle 380.0"
  s_max_pu: 0.7
  s_nom_max: .inf
  length_factor: 1.25
  under_construction: "zero"

links:
  p_max_pu: 1.0
  p_nom_max: .inf
  include_tyndp: true
  under_construction: "zero"

transformers:
```

```

x: 0.1
s_nom: 2000.
type: ""

atlite:
  nprocesses: 4
  cutouts:
    africa-2013-era5:
      module: era5
      dx: 0.3
      dy: 0.3

renewable:
  onwind:
    cutout: africa-2013-era5
    resource:
      method: wind
      turbine: Vestas_V112_3MW
    capacity_per_sqkm: 3
    copernicus:
      grid_codes: [20, 30, 40, 60, 100, 111, 112, 113, 114, 115, 116, 121, 122,
123, 124, 125, 126]
      distance: 1000
      distance_grid_codes: [50]
    natura: true
    potential: simple
    clip_p_max_pu: 1.e-2
    extendable: true
  offwind-ac:
    cutout: africa-2013-era5
    resource:
      method: wind
      turbine: NREL_ReferenceTurbine_5MW_offshore
    capacity_per_sqkm: 2
    correction_factor: 0.8855
    copernicus:
      grid_codes: [80, 200]
    natura: true
    max_depth: 50
    max_shore_distance: 30000
    potential: simple
    clip_p_max_pu: 1.e-2
    extendable: true
  offwind-dc:
    cutout: africa-2013-era5

```

```

resource:
  method: wind
  turbine: NREL_ReferenceTurbine_5MW_offshore
capacity_per_sqkm: 3
correction_factor: 0.8855
copernicus:
  grid_codes: [80, 200]
natura: true
max_depth: 50
min_shore_distance: 30000
potential: simple
clip_p_max_pu: 1.e-2
extendable: true
solar:
  cutout: africa-2013-era5
  resource:
    method: pv
    panel: CSi
    orientation: latitude_optimal
  capacity_per_sqkm: 4.6
  correction_factor: 0.854337
  copernicus:
    grid_codes: [20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 90, 100]
  natura: true
  potential: simple # or conservative
  clip_p_max_pu: 1.e-2
  extendable: true
hydro:
  cutout: africa-2013-era5
  resource:
    method: hydro
    hydrobasins: data/raw/hydrobasins/hybas_world_lev06_v1c.shp
    flowspeed: 1.0
    normalization: hydro_capacities
  carriers: [ror, PHS, hydro]
  PHS_max_hours: 6
  hydro_max_hours: "energy_capacity_totals_by_country" # not active
  clip_min_inflow: 1.0
  extendable: true
  normalization_multiplier: 1.1

costs:
  year: 2030
  discountrate: 0.07
  USD2013_to_EUR2013: 0.

```

```
marginal_cost:
  solar: 0.01
  onwind: 0.015
  offwind: 0.015
  hydro: 0.
  H2: 0.
  electrolysis: 0.
  fuel cell: 0.
  battery: 0.
  battery inverter: 0.
emission_prices:
  co2: 0.

solving:
  options:
    formulation: kirchhoff
    load_shedding: false
    noisy_costs: true
    min_iterations: 4
    max_iterations: 6
    clip_p_max_pu: 0.01
    skip_iterations: true
    track_iterations: false

  solver:
    name: gurobi
    threads: 4
    method: 2 # barrier (=ipm)
    crossover: 0
    BarConvTol: 1.e-5
    FeasibilityTol: 1.e-6
    AggFill: 0
    PreDual: 0
    GURO_PAR_BARDENSETHRESH: 200

plotting:
  map:
    figsize: [7, 7]
    boundaries: [-10.2, 29, 35, 72]
  p_nom:
    bus_size_factor: 5.e+4
    linewidth_factor: 3.e+3

costs_max: 800
```

```
costs_threshold: 1

energy_max: 15000.
energy_min: -10000.
energy_threshold: 50.

vre_techs: ["onwind", "offwind-ac", "offwind-dc", "solar", "ror"]
conv_techs: ["OCGT", "CCGT", "nuclear", "coal", "oil"]
storage_techs: ["hydro+PHS", "battery", "H2"]
load_carriers: ["AC load"]
AC_carriers: ["AC line", "AC transformer"]
link_carriers: ["DC line", "Converter AC-DC"]
tech_colors:
  "onwind": "#235ebc"
  "onshore wind": "#235ebc"
  "offwind": "#6895dd"
  "offwind-ac": "#6895dd"
  "offshore wind": "#6895dd"
  "offshore wind ac": "#6895dd"
  "offwind-dc": "#74c6f2"
  "offshore wind dc": "#74c6f2"
  "hydro": "#08ad97"
  "hydro+PHS": "#08ad97"
  "PHS": "#08ad97"
  "hydro reservoir": "#08ad97"
  "hydroelectricity": "#08ad97"
  "ror": "#4adbc8"
  "run of river": "#4adbc8"
  "solar": "#f9d002"
  "solar PV": "#f9d002"
  "solar thermal": "#ffef60"
  "biomass": "#0c6013"
  "solid biomass": "#06540d"
  "biogas": "#23932d"
  "waste": "#68896b"
  "geothermal": "#ba91b1"
  "OCGT": "#d35050"
  "gas": "#d35050"
  "natural gas": "#d35050"
  "CCGT": "#b20101"
  "nuclear": "#ff9000"
  "coal": "#707070"
  "lignite": "#9e5a01"
  "oil": "#262626"
  "H2": "#ea048a"
```

```
"hydrogen storage": "#b8ea04"
"battery": "#ea048a"
"Electric load": "#f9d002"
"electricity": "#f9d002"
"lines": "#70af1d"
"transmission lines": "#70af1d"
"AC-AC": "#70af1d"
"AC line": "#70af1d"
"links": "#8a1caf"
"HVDC links": "#8a1caf"
"DC-DC": "#8a1caf"
"DC link": "#8a1caf"
"load": "#FF0000"
"co2": "#FF0000"
nice_names:
  OCGT: "Open-Cycle Gas"
  CCGT: "Combined-Cycle Gas"
  offwind-ac: "Offshore Wind (AC)"
  offwind-dc: "Offshore Wind (DC)"
  onwind: "Onshore Wind"
  solar: "Solar"
  PHS: "Pumped Hydro Storage"
  hydro: "Reservoir & Dam"
  battery: "Battery Storage"
  H2: "Hydrogen Storage"
  lines: "Transmission Lines"
  ror: "Run of River"
```

C.2 Script for adding DAC to PyPSA-Africa

```

n.add("Carrier", "co2", co2_emissions=-1.0)
    #CO2 emissions value is from pypsa-earth-sec

#Atmosphere bus and store
n.add(
    "Bus",
    "co2 atmosphere",
    x= 46.738586,
    y= 24.774265,
    carrier="co2",
)

n.add(
    "Store",
    "co2 atm",
    e_nom_extendable=True,
    e_min_pu=-1,
    carrier="co2",
    bus="co2 atmosphere"
)

# this tracks CO2 stored, e.g. underground
co2_storage = n.madd(
    "Bus",
    buses_i + "co2 store",
    carrier="co2",
    **bus_sub_dict
)

co2_sequestration_cost= 10
#EUR/tCO2 for sequestration of CO2 from pypsa-earth-sec

efficiency2 = -(
    costs.at["DAC", "electricity-input"]
    + costs.at["DAC", "compression-electricity-input"])

n.madd(
    "Store",
    co2_storage,
    e_nom_extendable=True,
    e_nom_max=np.inf,
    capital_cost=co2_sequestration_cost,
    carrier="co2 stored",
)

```

```
        bus= co2_storage,
    )
    n.madd(
        "Link",
        buses_i + " DAC1",
        bus0="co2 atmosphere",
        bus1=buses_i,
        carrier="DAC",
        capital_cost=costs.at["DAC", "capital_cost"],
        efficiency=efficiency2,
        p_nom_extendable=True,
        lifetime=costs.at["DAC", "lifetime"],
    )
    n.madd(
        "Link",
        buses_i + " DAC2",
        bus0="co2 atmosphere",
        bus1=co2_storage,
        carrier="DAC",
        capital_cost=costs.at["DAC", "capital_cost"],
        efficiency=1,
        p_nom_extendable=True,
        lifetime=costs.at["DAC", "lifetime"],
    )
```

Appendix D: Health and Safety Form

Display Screen Equipment/Workstation Risk Assessment:

Introduction

The following checklist is designed to allow an assessment of individual Display Screen Equipment (DSE) workstations to be carried out, in terms of the Health and Safety (Display Screen Equipment) Regulations 1992, and associated guidance.

Users should be encouraged to carry out their own risk assessment, which will then be checked by the Local Safety Adviser. A new risk assessment needs to be carried out if there is a change of user, a change in equipment, or in location/set up.

Work through the checklist, ticking either the "yes" or "no" column against each risk factor:

- "yes" answers require no further action.
- "no" answers will require investigation and/or remedial action by the Local Safety Adviser. They should record their decisions in the "Action to take" column. Assessors should check later that actions have been taken and have resolved the problem.

Please note that, though a characteristic of the workstation may not precisely match the advice given in the Regulations and Guidance, remedial action will not require to be applied if the user in question is satisfied with the item, and desires no change.

Remember the checklist only covers the workstation and work environment. You also need to make sure that risks from other aspects of the work are avoided, for example by giving users health & safety training, and providing for breaks or changes of activity. Advice on these is given in the main text of the guidance.

Created on 08/08/2022

Record of Assessment

Workstation location: (School, Division, Unit etc., building, room no & floor)	<i>Main Library, Ground Floor, Several Workstations</i>
Name of User:	<i>Anas Algarei</i>
Assessment completed by:	<i>Anas Algarei</i>
Assessment checked by:	
Date of Assessment:	<i>15/08/2022</i>
Any further action needed? Yes / No Please specify action required.	<i>No</i>
<i>Follow up action completed on:</i>	

Assessment Checklist

Risk Factors	Yes / No	Things to Consider	Action to take
1. DISPLAY SCREENS			
Are the characters clear and readable?	✓	Make sure the screen is clean and cleaning materials are made available. Check that text and background colours work well together.	
Is the text size comfortable to read?	✓	Software settings may need adjusting to change text size.	
Is the image stable, i.e. free of flicker?	✓	Try using difference screen colours to reduce flicker, e.g. darker background and lighter text, increase refresh rate of monitor setting. If problem persists, contact your IT support.	

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Is the screen's specification suitable for it's intended use?	✓	For example, intensive graphic work or work requiring fine attention to small details may require large display screens.	
Are the brightness and /or contrast adjustable?	✓	Separate adjustment controls are not essential, provided the user can read the screen easily at all times.	
Does the screen swivel and tilt?	✓	Swivel and tilt need not be built in; you can add a swivel and tilt mechanism. However, you may need to replace the screen if: - Swivel/tilt is absent or unsatisfactory - Work is intensive; and/or -The user has problems getting the screen to a comfortable position. The height of the screen should be roughly at eye level. A monitor stand may be required. If using an LCD screen, ensure it is adjustable in height, alternatively use a monitor stand.	
Is the screen free from glare and reflections?	✓	Find the source of the reflections. You might need to move the screen or even the desk and/or shield the screen from the source of the reflections. Screens that use dark characters on a light background are less prone to glare and reflections.	
Is the user facing the screen.	✓	Position the screen in front of the user, to avoid any twisting.	
Are adjustable window coverings provided and in adequate	✓	Check that curtains/blinds are in good working order. If not, report to Estates and Buildings. If these measures do not work, consider anti-glare screen filters as a last	

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condition?			resort and seek specialist help.	
2. KEYBOARDS				
Is the keyboard separate from the screen?	✓		This is a requirement, unless the task makes it impracticable (e.g. where there is a need to use a portable computer).	
Does the keyboard tilt?	✓		Tilt need not be built in	
Is it possible to find a comfortable keying position? NO	✓		Try pushing the display screen further back to create more room for the keyboard, hands and wrists. Keep elbows close to the body, do not overstretch the arms. Users of thick, raised keyboards may need a wrist rest. Users may find the use of a compact mini-keyboard more comfortable.	
Does the user have good keyboard technique?	✓		Training can be used to prevent: - hands bent up at wrist - hitting the keys too hard - overstretching the fingers	
Are the characters on the keys easily readable?	✓		Keyboards should be kept clean. If characters still cannot be read, the keyboard may need modifying or replacing. Use a keyboard with a matt finish to reduce glare and/or reflection.	
3. MOUSE, TRACKBALL, ETC				
Is the device suitable for the tasks it is used	✓		If the user is having problems, try a different device. The mouse and trackball are general-purpose devices suitable for	

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for?			<p>many tasks, and available in a variety of shapes and sizes. Alternative devices such as touch screens may be better for some tasks (but can be worse for others).</p> <p>Check the device has been set to suit the user (for right or left hand user).</p>	
<p>Is the device positioned close to the user?</p>	✓		<p>Most devices are best placed as close as possible e.g. right beside the keyboard.</p> <p>Training may be needed to: -prevent arm overreaching -tell users not to leave their hand on the device when it is not being used - encourage a relaxed arm and straight wrist.</p> <p>A compact keyboard will help the user to avoid overreaching.</p>	
Is there support for the device user's wrist and forearm?	✓		<p>Support can be gained from, for example, the desk surface. If not, a separate supporting device (gel filled) may help.</p> <p>The user should be able to find a comfortable working position with the device.</p>	
Does the device work smoothly at a speed that suits the user?	✓		<p>Check if cleaning is required (e.g. of mouse ball and rollers).</p> <p>Check the work surface is suitable. A mouse mat may be needed.</p>	
Can the user easily adjust software settings for	✓		<p>Users may need training in how to adjust device settings.</p>	

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speed and accuracy of pointer?			
4. SOFTWARE			
Is the software suitable for the task?	✓	<p>Software should help the user carry out the task, minimise stress and be user-friendly.</p> <p>Check users have had appropriate training in using the software.</p> <p>Software should respond quickly and clearly to user input, with adequate feedback, such as clear messages.</p>	
5. FURNITURE			
Is the work surface large enough for all the necessary equipment, papers etc?	✓	<p>Create more room by moving printer, reference materials etc elsewhere. Use multilevel trays for papers/documents.</p> <p>If necessary, consider providing new power and telecom sockets, so equipment can be moved.</p> <p>There should be some scope for flexible rearrangement.</p>	
Can the user comfortably reach all the equipment and papers they need to use?	✓	<p>Rearrange equipment, papers etc to bring frequently used things within easy reach.</p> <p>A document holder may be needed, positioned to minimise uncomfortable head and eye movements.</p>	
Are the surfaces free from glare and reflection?	✓	<p>Consider mats or blotters to reduce reflections or glare.</p>	
Is the chair stable & suitable for the user?	✓	<p>The chair may need repairing or replacing if the user is uncomfortable, or the adjustment mechanisms are faulty.</p>	
Does the chair			

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have a working: - seat back height and tilt adjustment? - Seat height adjustment? - Swivel mechanism? - Castors or glides?		Contact the University Furniture Office.	
Is the chair adjusted correctly?	✓	<p>The user must be familiar with the chair adjustments.</p> <p>Adjust the chair height to sit with elbows at approx. 90° & 2cm above the desk when touching the G & H keys.</p> <p>The user should be able to carry out their work sitting comfortably.</p> <p>Consider training the user in how to adopt suitable postures while working.</p> <p>The arms of chairs can stop the user getting close enough to use the equipment comfortably. Consider chairs without armrests or alternatively, adjustable armrests.</p> <p>Move any obstructions from under the desk.</p>	
Is the lower back supported by the chair's backrest?	✓	The user should have a straight back, supported at all times by the chair, with relaxed shoulders.	
Are forearms horizontal and eyes at roughly the same height	✓	Adjust the chair height to get the user's arms in the right position; adjust the monitor height/tilt if necessary.	

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as the top of the screen?			
6. ENVIRONMENT			
Is there enough room to change position and vary movement?	✓	<p>Space is needed to move, stretch and fidget.</p> <p>Consider reorganising the office layout and check for obstructions.</p> <p>Cables should be tidy and not a trip or snag hazard.</p>	
Is the lighting suitable, e.g. not too bright or too dim to work comfortably?	✓	<p>Users should be able to control light levels, e.g. by adjusting window blinds or light switches.</p> <p>Consider shading or repositioning light sources or providing local lighting, e.g. desk lamps (but make sure lights don't cause glare by reflecting off walls or other surfaces).</p>	
Does the air feel comfortable?	✓	<p>VDUs and other equipment may dry the air. Green plants may help to increase moisture levels in the air.</p> <p>Circulate fresh air if possible.</p> <p>As a last resort, if discomfort is severe, consider a humidifier.</p>	
Are levels of heat comfortable?	✓	<p>Can heating be better controlled? More ventilation or air-conditioning may be required if there is a lot of electronic equipment in the room. Or, can users be moved away from the heat source?</p>	
Are levels of noise comfortable?	✓	<p>Consider moving sources of noise, e.g. printers, away from the user. If not, consider soundproofing.</p>	
7. ELECTRICAL			

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Have you carried out a user check (visual inspection) of the visually accessible parts of the equipment and it's cable, plug and extension cable.	✓	<p>See http://www.docs.csg.ed.ac.uk/Safety/Policy/Pa rt3.pdf for more information on user checks.</p> <p>Carry out a user check when the equipment has been relocated.</p> <p>Any faults or significant wear and tear, must be reported and repaired as soon as possible (contact your local computing support)</p> <p>Do not use any equipment if defective. Remove from operation and label 'DO NOT USE - EQUIPMENT FAULTY'.</p>	
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Final Questions to Users:

- Is a portable computer being frequently used?

Yes

If so, reduce its use to a minimum. Alternatively, have a docking station (separate keyboard, separate screen or screen elevated, separate mouse or tracking device). More detailed guidance on working with laptop computers is available at <http://www.docs.csg.ed.ac.uk/Safety/health/DSE.pdf>.

- Has the checklist covered all the problems the user may have working with the DSE?

Yes

- Has the user been advised of their entitlement to eye and eyesight testing, and advised to contact the Occupational Health Unit or the Health and Safety Office to arrange appropriate eye sight testing?

No

- Does the user take regular breaks working away from the DSE?

Yes

- Has the user read the leaflet "Are you keying comfortably"?

Yes

Who to Contact:

- For furniture replacement or repair, contact Furniture Office, Estates and Buildings 50 2077

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Produced by the Health and Safety Department, the University of Edinburgh

- For Blinds, curtains, etc EBIS Repair, Works Division
- For Computing equipment / software contact Information Services (i.e. normal contact)
- For Electrical defects contact Works Division 50 2485
- For Work environment factors (ventilation, noise, etc) contact Occupational Hygiene Unit Occupational.Hygiene@ed.ac.uk
- Following implementation and trial of any changes - For on-going Health issues related to DSE use contact the Occupational Health Unit 50 8190 / Occupational.Health@ed.ac.uk

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